

ARIES

Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 730871

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Report on advances in beam diagnostics for 3rd generation light sources

DELIVERABLE: D8.3

Document identifier:	ARIES-D8.3
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 54 (September 2021)
Justification for delay:	Delay related to COVID-19 pandemic concerning workshop organization
Report release date:	20/12/2021
Work package:	WP8: Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerators (ADA)
Lead beneficiary:	ALBA-CELLS
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

Section 5 of this Report covers the subject of Deliverable 8.3 (Advances in beam diagnostics for 3rd generation light sources). Sections 5.1 to 5.3 summarize the three International Workshops organised on this specific subject, and Section 5.4 presents some general conclusions on the status of this field and on possible future developments. In the Appendix, detailed descriptions of the three Workshops concerned are given.

ARIES Work Package 8 aims for transfer of knowledge and standardisation of equipment across the European Research Infrastructures making use of beam instrumentation and diagnostics for particle accelerators. In total, 11 International Workshops were organized with 32 to 239 delegates (maximum for a remote workshop). Financial support for visits of scientists was covered in total for eight weeks.

While in the initial Work Plan it was foreseen to produce as a Deliverable four separated Reports, one for each of the Tasks/sub-sets of diagnostic equipment, during the execution of the project it turned out the number of intercorrelations and crossed references between the four areas was so large that it was more effective to produce a single report, with four Sections each devoted to one of the Tasks/Deliverables.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors, please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730871. ARIES began in May 2017 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	P. Forck	GSI	16/12/21
Edited by	P. Forck	GSI	16/12/21
Reviewed by	M. Vretenar on behalf of Steering Committee	CERN	17/12/21
Approved by	Project Coordinator		20/12/21

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	5
2. WORK-PACKAGE COORDINATION (TASK 1).....	8
3. PROGRESS IN BEAM DIAGNOSTICS FOR HADRON LINACS (TASK 2).....	9
3.1 WORKSHOP ON ‘SIMULATION, DESIGN & OPERATION OF IONIZATION PROFILE MONITORS’	9
3.2 WORKSHOP ON ‘SCINTILLATION SCREENS AND OPTICAL TECHNOLOGY FOR TRANSVERSE PROFILE MEASUREMENTS’	9
3.3 WORKSHOP ON ‘EXPERIENCES DURING HADRON LINAC COMMISSIONING.’	10
3.4 CONCLUSION FOR HADRON LINAC BEAM DIAGNOSTICS	11
4. ADVANCES IN BEAM DIAGNOSTICS FOR HADRON SYNCHROTRONS (TASK 3)	13
4.1 WORKSHOP ON ‘EXTRACTING INFORMATION FROM ELECTROMAGNETIC MONITORS IN HADRON ACCELERATORS’ ..	13
4.2 WORKSHOP ON ‘NEXT GENERATION BEAM POSITION ACQUISITION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEMS’	13
4.3 WORKSHOP ON ‘MATERIALS AND ENGINEERING FOR PARTICLE ACCELERATOR BEAM DIAGNOSTIC INSTRUMENTS’	14
4.4 CONCLUSION FOR HADRON SYNCHROTRON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS	16
5. ADVANCES IN BEAM DIAGNOSTICS FOR 3RD GENERATION LIGHT SOURCES (TASK 4)18	
5.1 WORKSHOP ON ‘NEXT GENERATION BEAM POSITION ACQUISITION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEMS’	18
5.2 WORKSHOP ON ‘DIAGNOSTICS EXPERTS OF EUROPEAN LIGHT SOURCES (DEELS 19)’	18
5.3 WORKSHOP ON ‘DIAGNOSTICS EXPERTS OF EUROPEAN LIGHT SOURCES (DEELS 21)’	18
5.4 CONCLUSION FOR ELECTRON SYNCHROTRON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS	19
6. ADVANCES IN BEAM DIAGNOSTICS FOR FREE ELECTRON LASERS AND ELECTRON LINACS (TASK5)	21
6.1 WORKSHOP ON ‘EMITTANCE MEASUREMENTS FOR LIGHT SOURCES AND FELs’	21
6.2 WORKSHOP ON ‘LONGITUDINAL DIAGNOSTICS AT FREE ELECTRON LASERS’	21
6.3 CONCLUSION FOR ELECTRON LINAC BEAM DIAGNOSTICS	22
7. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK	24
8. REFERENCES	24
9. ATTACHMENTS.....	25

Executive summary

To meet the demands of new accelerator facilities, novel beam instrumentation and diagnostics methods are required. Beam instrumentation deals with versatile topics of applied physics and various technologies. The network 'Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerator' (ARIES-ADA) focused activities at various laboratories to initialize collaborations on a formal or, in most cases, informal basis. As a methodology, topical workshops related to one actual subject was chosen; moreover, the exchange of personnel between accelerator laboratories and universities is covered financially. Eleven topical workshops were organized; all workshops had participants from America, Asia and Europe. In three of these workshops, ARIES-ADA acts as a co-sponsor, leading to increasing contributions. Eight of these topical workshops were organized as a high-light event; each covers a topic that is not discussed in such detail at conferences and contributed significantly to a knowledge transfer between experts in various fields.

Eight of the workshops were executed as an in-person meeting between May 2017 and June 2019; depending on the subject, the number of delegates varied from 32 to 84. Personal contact is the key issue for sustainable collaborations, and those workshops contribute significantly to their initialization. The workshop duration was between one and three full days. The financial budget of ARIES-ADA was used to cover part of the costs of the workshops.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic initialized travel restrictions started in spring 2020, three workshops were organized as remote events between three and five half-days. The number of registrants was higher than the in-person meetings and increasing contributions.

In addition to the workshops, the budget was used to finance personnel exchanges for three scientists and duration between two and four weeks. In particular, early-stage scientists benefitted significantly. Several further visits were planned but could not be realized due to the travel restrictions that showed up at the end of 2019.

In contrary to the planned initially categories related to the different types of accelerators (hadron LINAC, hadron synchrotrons, circular light sources and linear light sources), it turned out that it is much more efficient to discuss in a common report the challenges related to various diagnostics methods, gaining from the synergy between the communities. Consequently, one more comprehensive deliverable report instead of four separate reports has been produced. The workshop content is shortly described in the main text, and detailed summaries of each workshop are attached as an appendix.

The subject of Deliverable 8.3 is therefore covered in Section 5 of the present Report.

1. Introduction

To meet the demands of new accelerator facilities, novel beam instrumentation and diagnostics methods are required leading to the permanent development of beam instruments. Versatile technologies are used based on many aspects of applied physics. The knowledge transfer between accelerator laboratories, universities, and industry is the focus of the ARIES work-package 8 network activity called ‘Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerator’ (ARIES-ADA). As the methodology, the organization of topical workshops related to one dedicated topic was chosen, offering the possibility of in-depth discussion on one subject not covered at typical conferences in such detail. A further aim is to initialize or intensify collaboration between the laboratories and strengthen the contact to industry for joint developments and efficient usage of available human resources. The industry is a relevant partner and contributed to several scientific talks the workshops.

Initially, it was planned to divide the work package into four tasks, namely related to hadron LINACs (Task 2 led by GSI), hadron synchrotrons (Task 3 led by CERN), circular synchrotron light source (Task 4 led by ALBA) and linear FEL light sources (Task 5 led by DESY). During the work-package execution, it turned out that this is not an efficient classification as most of the actual workshop topics comparably concerned several tasks. Due to this change of perspective, the planned initially individual Deliverable Reports D8.1 to D8.4 are now combined in a lengthy report covering the entire work-package program.

Eleven topical workshops were organized; all workshops had participants from America, Asia and Europe. Table 1 contains the compilation of the workshops, including the links to the INDICO site and some basic numbers cornering the duration, number of participants etc. For three of these workshops, ARIES-ADA acts as a co-sponsor, allowing for an increase of contributions. Eight of these topical workshops were organized as a high-light event; each covers an actual topic, which is not covered in such detail at typical conferences. The program ARIES-ADA contributed significantly to the knowledge transfer between experts in various fields in science and technology. In particular, engineers participated in those workshops, who usually are not contributing to regular conferences.

Eight of the workshops were executed as in-person meetings between May 2017 and June 2019; depending on the subject, the number of delegates varied from 32 to 84. Personal contact is the key issue for sustainable collaborations, and those workshops contribute significantly to their initialization. The workshop duration was between one and three full days. The financial budget of ARIES-ADA was used to cover part of the workshops costs and contributed to the travel costs of the workshop attendees. This allows for the participation of not only physicist but also engineers and technical personnel and people from outside of Europe where the home institutes might now be able to cover the full travel cost.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic initialized travel restrictions starting in spring 2020, three workshops were organized as remote workshops with a duration of between three and five half-days. The number of registrants was higher than in-person meetings, namely 49, 205 and 239. About 100 people were connected simultaneously during the presentation sessions for the last two workshops. The easier access without travels disabled a wider variety of contributions presented to a broader audience.

Personal discussions were still possible, in particular, when separated 'breakout rooms' were prepared beforehand by the workshop organizers.

Table 1: Compilation of topical workshops organized within the frame of ARIES-ADA; the columns are the date, main organizer, location of the workshop, title (linked to workshop INDICO-site), number of delegates the task which is mainly concerned and co-organizing tasks.

#	Date	Org. & location	Title of workshop	# Part.	main task	Contr. task
1	22-24 May 2017	GSI Darmstadt	Simulation, Design & Operation of Ionization Profile Monitors	33	2	3
2	29-30 Jan. 2018	ALBA & DESY Barcelona	Emittance Measurements for Light Sources and FELs	37	5	4
3	14-16 May 2018	CERN & GSI Geneva	Extracting information from electromagnetic monitors in Hadron Accelerators	32	3	4
4	25-27 June 2018	DESY & PSI Hamburg	Longitudinal Diagnostics at FELs (co-sponsoring)	45	5	-
5 & 6	12-14 Nov. 2018	ALBA & GSI Barcelona	Next Generation Beam Position Acquisition and Feedback Systems Two in one event: hadron & electron acc.	84	3 & 4	-
7	1-3 April 2019	GSI & SOLARIS Krakow	Scintillation Screens and Optical Technology for transverse Profile Measurements	49	2	4 & 5
8	3-5 June 2019	ALBA & ESRF Grenoble	Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources (DEELS 19) (co-sponsoring)	33	4	
9	25-29 Jan. 2021	CIEMAT & GSI Online	Experiences during Hadron LINAC Commissioning	239	2	
10	21-23 June 2021	CERN & GSI Online	Materials and Engineering for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments	205	3	2, 4 & 5
11	7-8 July 2021	ALBA & SESAME Online	Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources (DEELS 21) (co-sponsoring)	49	4	

Table 1 summarises the subjects of the workshops, including some basic numbers, such as the duration, the number of delegates, link to the workshop INDICO-site and the involved ARIES-ADA tasks. Several of the workshops were summarised at the beam instrumentation conference IBIC series for a larger audience, showing the relevance of the discussed projects and the importance of the funding by the European Community; clear credits are given to the EU funding. The related papers are:

- Invited talk at IBIC 2018 by Ubaldo Iriso: “Summary of Emittance Measurements Workshop for SLS and FELs”; no proceedings were written.
- Poster contribution at IBIC 2018 by Peter Forck: “ARIES-ADA: An R&D Network for Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerators”; related conference proceeding Ref. [1].

- Invited talk at IBIC 2019 by Beata Walasek-Höhne: “Screens for High Precision Measurements”; related conference proceeding Ref. [2].
- Invited talk at IBIC 2019 by Guenther Rehm: "Characterization of Closed Orbit Feedback Systems”; related conference proceeding Ref. [3].
- Contributed talk at IBIC 2021 by Peter Forck: “Summary of the ARIES Workshop on Materials and Engineering Technologies for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments”; related conference proceeding Ref. [4].

Most of the ARIES-ADA budget was used to cover the event costs such as venue rent, the cost for coffee breaks and refreshments and administrative issues. Some parts of the travel costs for delegates were covered; this enabled the participation of young scientists and people from institutes with a low amount of travel budget, increasing the intentionality of the events.

In addition to the workshops, the ARIES-ADA budget was used to finance the personnel exchanges for three scientists and duration between two and four weeks. In all cases, a relation to one of the workshop subjects exists. In particular, early-stage scientists benefitted significantly. The involved institutions were:

- A scientist from Fermilab (USA) visited GSI related to Ionization Profile Monitor development
- A scientist from the University of Milan visited ALBA related to high-resolution profile measurement at light sources
- A scientist from GSI visited Diamond Light Source related to the closed orbit feedback design at synchrotrons; this scientific discussion contributed to peer-reviewed journal articles Ref. [5, 6].

Several further visits were scheduled but could not be realized due to the travel restrictions that showed up at the end of 2019. It concerned visits of a Chinese scientist from IMP at GSI, a Jordanian scientist from SESAME at ALBA, two German scientists from GSI to the Brazilian light source SIRIUS.

Generally, the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the exchange of personnel, resulting in the complete cancellation of visits from the beginning of the year 2020. Workshops were foreseen as in-person events to enable a familiar atmosphere with senior people who met young scientist engineers to force discussions about layout details and 'tricks', which are usually not discussed at large conferences and were very helpful for successfully designing and operating beam instrumentation. Therefore, the planned workshops were postponed, hoping for in-person meetings in autumn 2020 to spring 2021. As it turned out that this was impossible, online workshops were organized. This format had the advantage that significantly more delegates participated, particularly from China, Japan, and Korea. In this sense, the scope was even widened, and the project ARIES is now well-known in the worldwide instrumentation community. However, a delay for ARIES-ADA was caused by the change of the workshop format and the related scope modification. Further workshops were initially planned but could not be realized in the remaining time frame.

To conclude: Thanks to the funding by the EU, the project ARIES-ADA organized special topic workshops covering actual subjects of great importance, strengthened the collaboration due to the workshops and the exchange of personnel, and were very positively recognized by the beam instrumentation community.

In the main text, the individual workshops are briefly summarised. A detailed workshop summary is attached for each workshop. It serves as an introduction to the individual contributions and is also published on the corresponding workshop INDICO-site. As different authors wrote the text, the style and length varied.

2. Work-package Coordination (Task 1)

The task leaders jointly executed the work-package coordination. Several informal meetings took place at conferences or other meetings of the related persons. For each workshop, dedicated teams were built together with the experts on the topic. Several non-beneficiary institutes contributed significantly, such as CIEMAT, ELETTRA, ESRF, FNAL, J-PARC, KEK, PSI, SOLARIS, SOLEIL, SNS, TRIUMF; in this sense, the work-package transformed into a successful international activity.

3. Progress in Beam Diagnostics for Hadron LINACs (Task 2)

3.1 WORKSHOP ON 'SIMULATION, DESIGN & OPERATION OF IONIZATION PROFILE MONITORS'

In May 2017, a Topical Workshop at GSI concerning '[Simulation, Design & Operation of Ionization Profile Monitors](http://indico.gsi.de/event/5366/)' (<http://indico.gsi.de/event/5366/>) with 33 participants from Europe, North America and Asia. It was organized as a joint event of Task 8.2 (hadron LINACs) and 8.3 (hadron synchrotrons). An Ionization Profile Monitor (IPM) is based on spatially resolving the ions or electrons generated from residual gas ionization via beam impact. These monitors deliver the beam profile in a non-destructive manner with a spatial resolution of typically 50 μm and time gating down to the 10 ns level. They are installed at both hadron LINACs and synchrotrons. Due to the increase in the beam power of future LINACs (e.g. at CERN, ESS, FAIR, ISIS) these IPMs will substitute the traditional invasive wire-based diagnostics. Even though the principle is well known, there are many technical challenges for such beam instrumentation's stable and reliable operation. The experts in the field presented the experience and technical solutions from installations worldwide. The results were extensively discussed, and the related contributions serve as a comprehensive catalogue of such systems.

The workshop's primary purpose was to introduce the community to a recently completed simulation code called IPMSim, <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/IPMSim/>. This code was produced with the input of several experts to simulate the related physical processes (cross-section for electron and ion production) under various conditions (beam distribution, space charge, external field configurations) from non-relativistic beams at LINACs to highly energetic beams at synchrotrons. The code features a modern programming style, a user-friendly GUI and can easily be expanded to include new physical models and applications. The code is freely available, and its benchmarking was successfully demonstrated. Further extensions of the code (e.g. for Beam Induced Fluorescence Monitors) are now realized. Possible experimental verifications of such simulations were put forward at this workshop, and several have now been performed.

As foreseen in the ARIES proposal, an exchange of personnel was made possible, with Dr. J. Zagel from Fermilab (USA) staying at GSI for several weeks to discuss IPM related topics and possible improvements to these systems at GSI.

3.2 WORKSHOP ON 'SCINTILLATION SCREENS AND OPTICAL TECHNOLOGY FOR TRANSVERSE PROFILE MEASUREMENTS'

The Topical Workshop '[Scintillation Screens and Optical Technology for transverse Profile Measurements](https://indico.cern.ch/event/765975/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/765975/>) took place in April 2019 in Krakow, Poland with 49 participants organized by GSI in collaboration with the Polish Light Source SOLARIS. It was a joint event of all tasks as scintillation screens are installed at almost every type of accelerator, including laser-plasma accelerators. Industrial partners contributed with three scientific talks. The

workshop included an industrial exhibition with four booths. A guided tour at SOLARIS took place on the third day.

The first topic of the workshop was related to the understanding of the scintillation process. Experts in inorganic scintillation research presented two overview talks discussing scintillator physics and recent technological developments. The regular application of scintillators at high energy physics, medical imaging or homeland security is focused on high sensitivity with a low count rate. In contrast to the application in beam instrumentation, the screen is directly irradiated by the primary beam, which might have a high flux within short bunches (e.g. at FEL facilities) or with high energy deposition (e.g. at ion facilities). Several scintillation materials were investigated for various beam parameters, and the results from several facilities were presented.

To achieve the required resolution for the profile measurements, dedicated optics has to be installed in the vicinity of the beam pipe. Detailed optical realizations were presented depicting solutions for these unusual geometries (e.g. Scheimpflug orientation). The advanced technical realizations at 3rd and 4th generation light sources were shown, and related experiences were discussed, including the suppression of coherent optical transition radiation.

The existing camera technologies were summarised by an industrial producer of high-performance cameras showing the pro and cons of the various sensor types. Radiation hardness tests of cameras were performed at CHARM@CERN, showing the requirements for novel cameras that survive the typical radiation levels at hadron facilities. Additionally, the usage of optical fibres was discussed.

A large fraction of the contributions discussed the properties of the different scintillators for hadron and electron beams. Experimental and theoretical investigations were presented concerning radiation damage by hadron beams, e.g. relevant for the target diagnostics at SNS and ESS. For intense electron beams, e.g. at DESY XFEL saturations effect were observed, and an explanation model was developed. The technical realization and the experiences at various facilities were discussed.

3.3 WORKSHOP ON 'EXPERIENCES DURING HADRON LINAC COMMISSIONING.'

The Topical Workshop '[Experiences during Hadron LINAC Commissioning](https://agenda.ciemat.es/event/1229/)' (<https://agenda.ciemat.es/event/1229/>) took place in January 2021 as a remote event jointly organized by CIEMAT and GSI comprising of five half-day sessions. 239 delegates registered, and about 100 people were simultaneously connected; see graphic in the detailed summary part. The interest by the community, as measured by the number of delegates, was significantly larger than anticipated. Initially, the workshop was planned for June 2020 as an in-person event.

Several proton and ion LINACs were commissioned in the past years, such as LINAC4, PIP-II, SARAF, Spiral2, or are in the commissioning phase, such as ESS FRIB, HELIAC, LIPAc. Even at existing LINACs, such as BNL, GSI, J-PARC, SNS, significant developments are ongoing, and reports on the related experiences are of mutual interest. The aims of this workshop were:

- Bring together instrument designers, experts, and research groups working on proton or ion linear accelerators' commissioning.
- Review the experiences on the commissioning of hadron LINACs from the first day of operation to more regular operation.

- Discuss the discrepancies between the beam instruments requirements specified at the design phase and the real needs and applications requirements during commissioning.
- Explore the feedback about the LINAC layout and usage of diagnostics test benches during stage-based commissioning.

Most of the contributions were given by experts responsible for the commissioning and operation of the LINACs. The speakers described the requirements formulated for the day-one operation to the time of regular operation and detailed accelerator physics investigations.

The experiences during step-wise commissioning (enabling detailed accelerator-physics investigations) were described and weighted to the quicker installation phase by installing a significant part of the LINAC in one step. For both attempts, the methodology was supported with various examples. These were essential statements for the beam diagnostics community for an appropriate instrumentation layout.

The use of various beam instrumentation was discussed with its data acquisition systems and graphical user interfaces. The potential for automatic beam alignment was investigated at several facilities using different methods, ranging from traditional deterministic algorithms to machine learning applications as a trendsetting topic. The realization and usage caused some controversial discussions.

On the fifth day, several speakers presented special instruments, which have, or will have, applications for operation and accelerator-physics investigations. Further speakers discussed the perspective of industry producing beam instrumentation or a significant part of a LINAC facility.

3.4 CONCLUSION FOR HADRON LINAC BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

The objective of the initial proposal aims for the reduction of losses and a safe operation of high power LINACs. This goal is reached, as several relevant topics related to non-invasive measurement techniques were discussed and are now improved. In particular, this concerns the non-invasive transverse profile measurement technology (discussed at the workshop section 3.1), applications for phase measurement (discussed at the third workshop, section 3.3), and automated beam manipulation techniques including machine learning algorithms (partly covered at the workshop section 3.3).

Non-invasive profile measurements are non-standard methods at high current LINACs but are required to allow for the observation of the entire macro-pulse; contrary to SEM-Grids or wire scanners that require a shortening of the macro-pulse to prevent for overheating. One subject of the topic workshop (section 3.1) was the technical realizations for IPMs at different facilities and information about construction details. As the main topic, the simulation code IPMSim were introduced to the community. In the time between the workshop (May 2017) and the drafting of the report (mid-2021), the code is significantly enhanced and now used at different labs. The code also includes the simulation of further non-invasive profile measurements such as Beam Induced

Fluorescence. Moreover, it can serve as a basis for supervised machine learning correction algorithms required for very intense beams at hadron LINACs and synchrotrons.

At the second workshop (section 3.2), applications for all types of accelerators related to scintillation screens were discussed. The general understanding of the process and its applicability was the workshop's main topic. Screens are applied regularly for profile measurements for hadron LINACs of low and medium intensities. The achievable light yield and possible radiation damage are of importance, and the workshop contributed to the understanding of the related physical processes enabling an appropriate choice of the scintillation material. For high current LINACs, pepper-pot emittance relay on the usage of screens, and innovative proposals were discussed. In addition, the applicability of scintillation screens for laser-accelerated beams were presented. Innovative camera technology for low light detection was an additional topic. Radiation hardness differs for several scintillator materials, and an appropriate choice is of great relevance at high power hadron LINACs.

The third workshop (section 3.3) concerned the central topic for beam instrumentation and their usage during the LINAC commissioning, and first stages of operation. People from instrumentation, operation and beam dynamics contributed in a balanced manner. It is interesting to note that phase measurements are vital to achieve the matching between the accelerating cavities and serve as one of the essential alignment tools. Automatic cavity amplitude and phase alignment methods were successfully applied at several facilities. First trials concerning automatic beam steering based on machine learning were discussed, proving the applicability of modern techniques. The improvement of those technologies is one of the objectives of ARIES-ADA. In general, the comparison of achievements at various facilities serves as a solid basis for future LINACs and their commissioning.

The workshop on mechanical issues (summarized below in section 4.3) contained many aspects relevant for hadron LINACs. This concerns, e.g. the production of SEM-Grid and wire scanners using Carbon Nano Tubes. Moreover, adaptive manufacturing is demonstrated with these instruments leading to an optimized production method; the vacuum requirements can be fulfilled. Novel methods for blackening of vacuum chambers are of great relevance for the non-invasive profile measurement method by Beam Induced Fluorescence. This photon detection method is an alternative to IPMs and brought into operation at several LINACs in the last years. Magnetically controlled vacuum drives are an excellent alternative to bellow-based drives due to their enhanced lifetime.

4. Advances in Beam Diagnostics for Hadron Synchrotrons (Task 3)

4.1 WORKSHOP ON 'EXTRACTING INFORMATION FROM ELECTROMAGNETIC MONITORS IN HADRON ACCELERATORS'

A topical workshop with 32 participants on '[Extracting Information from electromagnetic monitors in Hadron Accelerators](https://indico.cern.ch/event/705430/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/705430/>) took place in May 2018 at CERN. The goal was to strengthen the collaboration between the beam dynamics and beam instrumentation community as both communities have to contribute to a correct interpretation of advanced beam measurement methods. Additionally, people working at circular light sources participated as the topic is equally essential for the electron- and hadron synchrotrons.

The workshop focused on various measurement methods of lattice parameters at synchrotrons, such as the machine tune and chromaticity. Recent results concerning betatron-function measurement and beta-beating determination were discussed. The different methods used for optics measurements were summarised in an overview talk. It was shown that part of the progress is related to improvements in the BPM readout's achievable accuracy. The applicability of methods leading to significant noise reduction of the BPM data was demonstrated in several contributions. Moreover, the determination of advanced parameters such as intensity-dependent tune shift and tune spread determined via quadrupolar oscillations is a hot topic and intensively discussed between instrumentation and beam dynamics experts. A comparison between simulations and measurements at CERN PS shows a good correspondence, as had been depicted in one of the contributions.

Further on, Schottky signal analysis was discussed in several contributions. This method enables the observation of many parameters such as momentum spread, tune, chromaticity without any influence on the beam. The applicability for coasting and bunched beams for daily operation and detailed machine studies were discussed. The advanced Schottky system at LHC was recently commissioned and enabled online determination, e.g. of tune and chromaticity. Using Schottky analysis, it is possible to perform BPM-based position measurements for coasting beams. The collection of all those contributions serve as a comprehensive collection of the standard and advanced applications.

4.2 WORKSHOP ON 'NEXT GENERATION BEAM POSITION ACQUISITION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEMS'

The Topical Workshop on '[Next Generation Beam Position Acquisition and Feedback Systems](https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/>) was organized as a joint event between task 8.3 (hadron synchrotron) and 8.4 (circular light sources). It took place in Barcelona in November 2018 with 84 participants. The first day was related to the analogue and digital electronics for BPMs at hadron synchrotrons, the second day as a joint event related to the closed orbit feedback systems and the third day with the subject of bunch-by-bunch feedback system at light sources to cure instabilities. Industrial partners contributed with two scientific talks.

The design considerations of analogue and digital electronics for the BPMs at hadron synchrotrons were presented on the first day. In particular, the methods to achieve the required resolution and

accuracy were discussed. Here the injection of a 'pilot tone' seems to be an excellent method; it is based on the injection of a signal beside the acceleration frequency band followed by appropriate filtering to distinguish between the injected signal and the beam signal. Further realizations of analogue electronics were discussed. An alternative to commercial products was shown for digital electronics based on 'open hardware repository' www.ohwr.org (hardware solutions can be copied under a GNU-type licence); GSI and Brazilian Light Source reported on positive experiences.

The closed orbit feedback system at electron and hadron synchrotrons was compared on the second day. Many familiar aspects exist, even though the applications seem to be different: At electron synchrotrons, mainly mechanical vibrations lead to closed orbit distortions, while hysteresis effects are more critical at hadron booster rings. An increase of the feedback bandwidth is envisaged for the next-generation light sources to improve the damping rate significantly. Presently, the latency for the feedback system is mainly given by the bandwidth of the corrector power suppliers; a contribution from PSI summarised their power supplier developments. Further on, the controller types and the mathematical basis for the inversion of the orbit response matrix were discussed, and the applicability of novel feedback algorithms was reported based on general symmetry considerations on Discrete Fourier Transformation, which have some advantages over the traditional Singular Value Decomposition.

The third day was devoted to the fast, bunch-by-bunch feedback system. A general overview was given in a talk by an industrial partner. The different realizations at the various facilities were discussed using either commercial hardware or unique homemade designs. The feedback system can also be used to monitor the beam's growth rates for detailed machine studies.

A related exchange of personnel took place in June 2018 by the GSI employee Sajjad Hussain Mirza to work for two weeks at the UK Diamond Light Source on topics related to closed orbit feedback. The collaboration led to a peer-reviewed journal article [5].

4.3 WORKSHOP ON 'MATERIALS AND ENGINEERING FOR PARTICLE ACCELERATOR BEAM DIAGNOSTIC INSTRUMENTS'

The Topical Workshop '[Materials and Engineering for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments](https://indico.cern.ch/event/863675/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/863675/>) was organized by CERN and GSI in connection the Department of Engineering Science of University-Oxford and concerned all ARIES-ADA tasks. It took place as a remote event in June 2021 for three half-days. 205 delegates were registered, and about 100 people participated simultaneously, see graphic in the detailed workshop summary.

As a novelty for these workshops, the speakers of the individual sessions were asked to enter separate breakout rooms to enable a discussion with interested workshop participants. As the workshop's topics are not very frequently presented at conferences, the individual private discussions were intensively used to clarify details and enable personal contacts. This procedure was very well accepted, and intense discussions on dedicated topics were executed.

Initially, the workshop was planned as an in-person meeting in Oxford end of March 2020 with 50 participants and 32 talks. However, it was cancelled only two weeks in advance due to the pandemic's start in Europe.

The workshop was targeted to the design and technology of physical instruments, which receives relatively little coverage in conferences and existing scientific literature. This finding might be caused by the fact that engineers rarely participate in regular conferences; however, most contributions were given by the engineers working on the beam instrument design in this workshop. The focus was on advanced mechanical concepts, design and technologies for realizations. The discussed topics were related to:

- Novel materials and production, e.g. ultra-thin wires for wire scanners and SEM-Grid
- Novel materials for vacuum installations with improved properties
- Precise vacuum installations and drives, e.g. magnetically coupled
- Improved methods for mechanical development & production, e.g. 3-d printing
- Review the state-of-the-art materials & production technologies.

The first topic of the workshops concerned wire scanners and SEM-Grids. Even though this seems to be an old technology, the challenge for linear light sources is the production of thin wires in the order of only 1 μm , which was realized for SwissFEL and FERMI and successfully tested. With this technology, beam sizes down to 0.5 μm can be resolved. For the fast wire scanner, as, e.g. used at CERN synchrotrons, the stability of the wire is an issue due to the enormous acceleration to a velocity of 20 m/s and the thermal resilience related to the immense beam power. The usage of novel Carbon Nano Tubes is a solution investigated with several methods at CERN and University-Oxford. The design of the motor, vacuum components and position reading have to use novel techniques as well.

Adaptive manufacturing by 3D printing of the fast scanner's wire fork was demonstrated as a mechanically complex device; the forks are now in regular operation. The vacuum compatibility of the 3D printed devices was demonstrated. Practical experiences for the 3d printing process were discussed in a separate talk, showing the applicability of this method for several further examples. The production method of SEM-Grid at CERN was discussed to produce an equally stressed wire array. Moreover, good experiences were reported for in-vacuum usage of so-called flex PCBs for the insulated connection between the SEM-Grid and the vacuum flange.

Two further applications of Nano Tubes were introduced at the workshop. The first application concerns the blackening of vacuum components; as reported by the company Vantablack, reflections below 0.1 % can be achieved. Secondly, a scintillator can be produced from boron-nitride for transverse profile measurements; functional tests with electron and ion beams were executed, proving the superior functionality.

The manufacturer described a novel generation of vacuum drives using magnetical coupling. The achievements are related to low magnetic stray fields, achievable precision of the movement, and ultra-high vacuum compatibility using novel grease-free metal rolling bearing. Detailed outgassing measurements of polymers were discussed, giving a good overview of the usability of insulators for in-vacuum installations. New sealing technologies for large vacuum flanges were successfully tested at DESY. Moreover, the proposed substitution of the regular stainless steel 316NL by 'Alloy 50' is used for ultra-high vacuum applications.

4.4 CONCLUSION FOR HADRON SYNCHROTRON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

The objective of this task was to establish methods for precise position measurement and orbit feedback, as well as the determination of lattice functions. Both topics were extensively covered by the workshops described in sections 4.1 and 4.2.

The first topic workshop (section 4.1) brought together beam dynamics and instrumentation experts to discuss the information required and achievable to increase the understanding and operational usage of electromagnetic monitors. Innovative numerical analysis methods can significantly improve an existing BPM system's capability. Modification of the recorded BPM frequency spectrum can be related to beam intensity effects. In particular, if dipole or quadrupole Beam Transfer Functions are executed, a theory-based interpretation is required to model related effects. Schottky signal analysis delivers rich information on the momentum distribution, transverse and longitudinal tunes, and chromaticity. As for the BTF, intensity effects modify the frequency spectrum, and the workshop contributed significantly to knowledge transfer between the beam dynamics and instrumentation community.

The objective of precise beam position measurement was one of the topics of the second workshop (section 4.2). Gain stability of the analogue electronics is a complex design challenge to achieve the required position accuracy, and experiences on the engineering level were discussed in detail. In particular, the 'pilot tone' injection method is now implemented at several hadron and electron synchrotrons to improve position accuracy. The exchange of experiences for both accelerator types can significantly improve the realization of next-generation electronics. The 'open hardware repository' can serve as a basis for efficient electronics production. Advanced digital evaluation methods can improve the resolution and the robustness against electromagnetic interference. The topic of closed orbit feedback is comparable for hadron and electron synchrotrons, even though the source of disturbance might be different. The advantages of novel correction algorithms based on general principles (DFT versus SVD decomposition, see Ref. [5]) were described and adapted for the application at different synchrotrons.

The workshop on material and engineering (section 4.3) was organized by this task to discuss modern trends in mechanical engineering, which concerns all types of accelerators. For the synchrotron applications, adaptive manufacturing is of excellent innovation potential as complex structures can be produced; it was shown that the vacuum requirements could be fulfilled. Secondly, Nano Tube material has its applications for wire scanners due to low weight and high mechanical stability; both technologies were applied for the CERN synchrotrons. Such blackening with Nano Tubes was recently installed in the LHC for Beam Induced Fluorescence profile measurements. Further meaningful experiences were reported at this workshop and will support the engineering design of beam instrumentation.

The third objective of this task, namely non-invasive profile measurements, was discussed in the workshop on IPMs (described above in section 3.1). For the transverse profile measurements in synchrotrons, a significant measured profile deformation might occur for intense beams. The code IPMSim can simulate this effect and is recently used for machine learning-based corrections as introduced during the workshop. Supervised learning via Neuronal Network related to image

recognition serves as an innovative method and progresses significantly in the meantime from the workshop to the drafting of this report (May 2017 to 2021).

5. Advances in Beam Diagnostics for 3rd Generation Light Sources (Task 4)

5.1 WORKSHOP ON 'NEXT GENERATION BEAM POSITION ACQUISITION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEMS'

The Topical Workshop on '[Next Generation Beam Position Acquisition and Feedback Systems](https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/>) was organized as a joint event between task 8.3 (hadron synchrotron) and task 8.4 (circular light sources) and is summarized above in section 4.2.

5.2 WORKSHOP ON 'DIAGNOSTICS EXPERTS OF EUROPEAN LIGHT SOURCES (DEELS 19)'

The Topical Workshop [Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources \(DEELS19\)](https://indico.cern.ch/event/789811/) (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/789811/>) took place in June 2019 in Grenoble with 33 participants jointly organized by ESRF and ALBA. It is based on a series of yearly meetings established six years ago. Thanks to the funding by ARIES, colleagues from Asia and America could participate.

As the main workshop topic, multiple projects of new electronics developments for Beam Position Monitors (BPM) were presented. Those new developments are motivated by two reasons: Firstly, the recent progress in FPGA chips open new possibilities and, secondly, stringent requirements for orbit feedback at ultra-low emittance synchrotrons. A BPM platform currently developed by ELETTRA focuses on modularity; it uses the 'pilot-tone' scheme to calibrate the analogue front-end and cable transmission drifts. High performances FGPA and Analog to Digital Converters are used at other facilities to achieve bunch-by-bunch measurements.

Concerning BPM measurement resolution and accuracy, some presentations focused on sources of error, together with proposed solutions to increase BPM performances and mitigate imprecise settings. This concerns online rf-measurements (like 'pilot-tone' injection) and statistical methods to enable a software-based online correction. Moreover, the effect of temperature and humidity on RF cables' transmission was investigated extensively.

As a further topic, ALBA presented a versatile software tool called "BPMLab" to compute the position resolution of a BPM; ESRF presented the software OASYS for synchrotron radiation simulations. Other topics were related to spatially resolved beam loss measurements using a scintillating fibre with modern light detectors (SiPM) at ALBA. Further BLM systems were described. Overview talks covered recent development for longitudinal diagnostics at SPRING8 and a THz diagnostics beamline design.

5.3 WORKSHOP ON 'DIAGNOSTICS EXPERTS OF EUROPEAN LIGHT SOURCES (DEELS 21)'

The Topical Workshop '[Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources \(DEELS 21\)](https://indico.cern.ch/event/1027295/)' (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/1027295/>) of task 8.4 (circular light sources) took place in July 2021 as

a remote event jointly organized by ALBA and SESAME as a one plus half-day event. It was the first time the mid-east facility hosted such a workshop of this type. 49 participants from 20 institutions were registered, among them delegates from universities in Egypt and Pakistan and 2 industrial companies.

One topic was the SESAME facility and its beam instrumentation which was not discussed in such detail at previous workshops. The audience was impressed by the progress made for this light source and the use of solar panels to supply the required energy for this machine. This is a clear example of green energy in the accelerator environment. In addition, the workshop included a virtual guided tour at this facility.

A second focus of the workshop was related to photon diagnostics. It comprised the design and usage of X-ray BPMs, which are nowadays foreseen as part of the closed orbit stabilization system. For the novel ultra-low emittance storage rings, such devices will serve as the primary monitors to fulfil the extreme demands on beam stability. The technical realization at Diamond, SESAME and SOLEIL was presented.

Other topics were related to techniques for bunch length recording using visible light, as realized at ESRF, and is now in operation. An innovative image reconstruction method by an Artificial Neural Network was realized for the transverse profile measurement at ALBA. The related method caused an intensive discussion.

5.4 CONCLUSION FOR ELECTRON SYNCHROTRON BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

The first objective of this task, namely the implementation of a performant orbit feedback, was discussed together with the experts from hadron synchrotrons (section 4.2). Combining the experiences from hadron and electron synchrotron applications, an overview of the state-of-the-art realizations could be achieved, and novel digital correction algorithms were successfully applied, see above in section 4.4. At this workshop, the properties of bunch-by-bunch feedback systems to cure beam instabilities were discussed, and their realizations at several light sources were presented. A commercial solution is available, designed by a leading scientist in the field. Improvements of the ultra-low emittance light sources are required, and the network of experts can contribute to the realization of the various projects. The contribution by engineers assigned to the realization of fast signal processing was a major achievement of the workshop.

Even though, the DEELS workshops were established prior to the start of ARIES-ADA, the co-sponsoring contributes to an enlargement of participants from Asia and America. This led to additional delegates and contributions to the topic (section 5.2 and 5.3). It is a success that SESAME (Jordan) contribute now to the workshop (due to the COVID-19 crisis, the planned in-person workshop could not be realized). Accurate position reading is a major beam diagnostic and will get even more challenging for the ultra-low emittance rings. State-of-the-art technical realizations were discussed at both meetings in detail. 'Pilot tone' injection can improve the accuracy of the analogue signal chain, and FPGA-based position calculation codes are shared between the institutes. The inclusion of X-ray BPMs (detecting the photon beam) into the closed orbit feedback is foreseen for several light source upgrades and is a new challenge, and a network can collect ideas leading to first technical designs.

The objective of innovative transverse profile measurement methods was intensively discussed at the workshop summarized in section 6.1 below. For the ultra-low emittance rings, the beam size is only several μm , and the traditional methods are insufficient. Significant improvements of the existing methods are urgently required to achieve the required resolution, or novel technologies must be applied. Various attempts were discussed during the workshop, and a compilation of the present status are summarized in Table 2; more details are described in the attached detailed workshop summary. This table serves as a reference for any future development. The discussion on the best-suited method is still ongoing and await the practical demonstration at several facilities.

Table 2: Comparison of profile measurement methods at circular light sources using synchrotron light monitors in the visible or X-ray range: The used technology and the achieved spatial resolution are given together with the presenter's name of the workshop contribution.

Method for <u>circular</u> accelerator	smallest σ [μm] (measured)	Workshop Presenter
Scintillator (reference)	1.5	G. Kube (DESY)
X-ray Pinhole	7	L. Bobb (DLS)/ F. Ewald (ESRF)
Comp. Refractive Lenses	10	F. Ewald (ESRF)/ A. Snigirev (Kalin.)
Vis. Light Interf.	3.9	T. Mitsuhashi (KEK)
Vis. Light Inter. (mask)	2 (sim)	L. Torino (ESRF)
p-polarization (vis)	3.7	A. Andersson (MAXLab)
Coded Aperture	5	J. Flanagan (KEK)
In-air X-ray Det.	9	F. Ewald (ESRF)
X-ray Diffraction	4.8	A. Snigirev (Kaliningrad)
X-ray (multi/lens) Inter.	4.8	A. Snigirev (Kaliningrad)
HNFS	130	M. Siano (Milan)

6. Advances in Beam Diagnostics for Free Electron Lasers and Electron LINACs (Task5)

6.1 WORKSHOP ON 'EMITTANCE MEASUREMENTS FOR LIGHT SOURCES AND FELs'

The Topical Workshop '[Emittance Measurements for Light Sources and FELs](https://indico.cells.es/indico/event/128/)' (<https://indico.cells.es/indico/event/128/>) was held at ALBA in January 2018, organized by Task 8.4 (circular light sources) with the collaboration of Task 8.5 (linear light sources). The workshop addressed challenges for the next generation of ultra-low emittance machines and LINAC-based FELs. One day was devoted to emittance measurements at synchrotron light sources and the second day at Free Electron Lasers. Experts working on emittance measurements for other types of machines, such as hadron synchrotrons and Laser Plasma Accelerators were also invited to discuss possible synergies between the different communities.

For synchrotron light sources, the review of present techniques using synchrotron radiation showed that beam sizes down to the 2-3 μm level could be measured through the careful design and choice of instrumentation. These techniques include direct imaging techniques (X-ray pinhole cameras, Compound Refractive Lenses, or in-air X-ray detectors) and techniques based on the analysis of light coherence (visible light interferometers). Since this is at the limit for the beam sizes foreseen for the next generation of low emittance rings, the benefits of more complex techniques such as X-ray diffraction/interferometry and Heterodyne Speckle Fields (HNFS) were also profoundly discussed during the workshop. The workshop concluded that these techniques would need specific beamlines foreseen for their operation.

For Free Electron Lasers, beam sizes are typically measured using invasive methods through the beam's interaction with movable obstacles, such as Optical Transition Radiation screens or wire scanners. It was shown that wires as thin as 1 μm can now be manufactured using lithographic techniques, which allows the measurement of beam sizes down to 500 nm. In addition, the current status of techniques such as laser wire measurements or Optical Diffraction Radiation Interferometry, the workshop also addressed new, innovative techniques such as those using Cherenkov Diffraction Radiation.

An exchange of personnel was organized within the frame of this workshop, with M. Siano (Univ. Milano) staying at ALBA to discuss the HNFS technique and to perform tests in an ALBA beamline.

6.2 WORKSHOP ON 'LONGITUDINAL DIAGNOSTICS AT FREE ELECTRON LASERS'

The Topical Workshop '[Longitudinal Diagnostics for Free-Electron Lasers](https://indico.cern.ch/event/702602/)', (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/702602/>) took place in June 2018 at DESY with 45 participants. The workshop aimed to foster joint developments of longitudinal diagnostics for femtosecond electron bunches and bring together experts working on beam instrumentation and detector development. Several participants working in the field of Laser Plasma Accelerators contributed to the workshop as these novel short-bunch accelerators face even higher demands concerning the time resolution. The topic of transverse deflecting structures (TDS) was intentionally excluded as there is a strong collaboration between CERN, PSI, and DESY on developing an X-Band TDS with regular meetings.

The workshop was organized in 5 working groups to exchange ideas, plan collaborations or measurement campaigns. The first day of the workshop was devoted to discussions within these working groups. On the second and third days, the working group coordinators reported the discussion results, and the participants presented their contributions in poster sessions.

Compression Monitors and THz Detectors: The intense coherent THz and IR part of diffraction or edge radiation emitted by the electron bunches is commonly used as a compression monitor for feedback on the accelerator phase. The THz/IR beam transport, attenuation and detection need to be optimized depending on the bunch charge, profile and repetition rate. Further improvements of a multi-array Schottky diode detector developed by TU Dresden as a THz spectrometer were identified.

Electro-Optical Diagnostics: Electro-optical techniques are limited in time resolution but are entirely non-invasive. Different readout schemes were discussed to achieve single-bunch resolution at MHz repetition rates. Joint experiments were planned.

THz Streak of the primary electron beam: The goal of this working group was to discuss possibilities to streak the electron beam in a micro-structure operating at THz frequencies. The aim is to improve the resolution of radio frequency deflectors by increasing both frequency and deflecting fields. The application to low-energy beams has been presented, and further studies at high-energy facilities were planned.

KALYPSO and fast digitization: The KALYPSO (Kalruhe Linear detector for MHz-rePetition rate Spectroscopy) linear detector system has been developed as a flexible digitizer board to be compatible with different front-end electronic standards for many applications. Requirements for the next improved version were defined by the various applications of the linear detector board.

Laser Heater operation and diagnostics: The aim was to share the experience of laser heater operation and optimization for the suppression of micro-bunching instabilities gained at different facilities. The cathode material of the photo-injector, e.g. Cu or Ce₂Te, seems to influence the micro-bunching instabilities and, in addition to that, on the operation of the laser heater. Further joint studies were discussed.

6.3 CONCLUSION FOR ELECTRON LINAC BEAM DIAGNOSTICS

Transverse profile measurements are a major tool for beam alignment and accelerator development for the linear light sources. Intersecting methods are frequently used but must be designed with great care. One topic is the suppression of coherent optical transition. More complex photon-detection methods were discussed, like diffraction radiation interferometry or the usage of Cherenkov radiation. These methods are pretty complex, and technical realizations are presently ongoing; design ideas were interchanged during the workshop (section 6.1). Another route is the usage of wire scanners with ultra-thin wires produced by lithographic processes. Laser wire scanners based on the inverse Compton effect act as an alternative; however, they are not technically a standard operational tool. One major outcome of the workshop was a comparison of resolution achievement for the various methods depicted in table 3; more details are discussed in the attached workshop summary. The production details of thin wire scanners were one major part of the workshop on material and engineering (section 4.3), where beam-based measurements demonstrated the technical realization.

Table 3: Comparison of different methods at linear light sources. The used technology and the achieved spatial resolution is given together with the presenter's name of the workshop contribution.

Method for <u>linear</u> accelerator	smallest σ [μm] (measured)	Workshop Presenter
Scintillator (reference)	1.5	G. Kube (DESY)
OTR Techniques	1.5	L. Sukhikh (Tomsk)
ODRI Techniques	??	E. Chiadroni (INFN)
COTR Techniques	3.8	A. Potylitsyn (Tomsk)
Wire Scanner Technique	0.490	K. Wittenburg (DESY) / S. Borrelli (PSI)
Laser Wire Technique	0.070	P. Karataev (RHUL)
Multi-Slit Mask Technique	200	M. Kraskilnikov (DESY)

Transverse profile measurements for linear light sources motivated the workshop on scintillation screens (section 3.2) to overcome the image deformation by coherent optical transition radiation. Hence, scintillating screens are presently used at FEL facilities. A given material's scintillation properties play a significant role in preventing, e.g. for saturation effects. Discussion between instrumentation specialists and manufacturers' representatives led to more appropriate customized design considerations. To achieve the required spatial resolution in the order of 1 μm , dedicated optical systems must be installed; the recent realization at DESY and PSI serves as a reference.

The central objective of bunch length measurement was covered by one workshop (section 6.2). It was a lengthy workshop with world-leading delegates and detailed working group discussions. In addition, the workshop included poster sessions. Major technologies were presented: Electro-optical methods and THz serve as complementary methods; the general layouts and technical realizations were discussed in detail. Experiences with laser-heaters for the instability suppressing widened the spectrum of activities with this workshop. The workshop serves as a comprehensive summary concerning the state-of-the-art diagnostics method for bunch length measurements.

Another objective, namely the high precision position monitoring, was partly covered in the related workshop described in section 4.2. Methods like 'pilot tone' injection and other technical realizations can also be applied at linear light sources.

The last objective concerning beam loss localization and fast interlock generation could not be covered due to the COVID-19 crisis as the task leader could not arrange a workshop in a remote format.

7. Conclusion and Outlook

The Topical Workshops within the frame of ARIES-ADA had a high impact on the development of advanced beam instrumentation. World-leading experts participated in the workshops as well as newcomers, who now take over in the development of novel instrumentation; in this sense, a durable network was initialized. In most of the workshops, engineers participated as well; they contribute significantly to the success of any beam instrumentation but, in many cases, do not participate significantly in conferences. The mixture of these experts contributed to the very positive 'flavour' of the workshop and contribute to the development of accelerators. The relevance of such workshops can be measured through the interest shown for each event by the worldwide audience: 32 – 84 delegates for in-person meetings and 49 to 239 for remote meetings. In particular, for the in-person events, a familiar atmosphere was created with senior people who met young scientist engineers to force discussions about layout details and 'tricks', which usually are not discussed at large conferences, which is very helpful for designing and operating beam instrumentation successfully. The program could be adapted to the pandemic situation after some delay by remote meetings. This format led to a larger and broader spread amount of delegates; with the help of breakout rooms, some discussions and personal contacts could still be established.

The obtained collection of high-quality contributions serves as a comprehensive reference summarising the actual status of these fields and proposals for further developments as gained from experience at the various accelerator facilities. In this sense, the ARIES-ADA Network Activity is an essential contribution to the general accelerator R&D. Almost every objective described in the original proposal were addressed and led to enhanced network activities. Moreover, additional topics were discussed in dedicated workshops on scintillation screens and material and engineering issues, which widened the scope towards innovations.

The workshop results were summarised at several conferences and scientific publications for a larger audience. The program ARIES is now well-known to the beam instrumentation community.

It is recommended to continue such topical workshops in future, as it is an efficient way of knowledge transfer and related personal contact. This will lead to man-power saving collaborations that justify the financial budget invested in covering travel expenses for in-person meetings.

8. References

- [1] P. Forck, M. Sapinski, C. Gerth, K. Wittenburg, U. Iriso, F. Pérez, R. Ischebeck, and O.R. Jones, "ARIES-ADA: An R&D Network for Advanced Diagnostics at Accelerators", in Proc. 7th Int. Beam Instrumentation Conf. (IBIC'18), Shanghai, China, Sep. 2018, pp. 71-74. [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2018-MOPB02](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2018-MOPB02).
- [2] B. Walasek-Höhne, P. Forck, K. Höhne, R. Ischebeck, and G. Kube, "Screens for High Precision Measurements", in Proc. 8th Int. Beam Instrumentation Conf. (IBIC'19), Malmö, Sweden, Sep. 2019, pp. 242-248. [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-TUBO01](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-TUBO01).

-
- [3] G. Rehm, "Characterization of Closed Orbit Feedback Systems", in Proc. 8th Int. Beam Instrumentation Conf. (IBIC'19), Malmö, Sweden, Sep. 2019, pp. 479-484. [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-WECO01](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2019-WECO01).
- [4] R. Veness, R. Jones, U. Iriso, G. Kube, K. Wittenburg, P. Forck, V. Schlott, and D. Eakins "Summary on ARIES-ADA virtual Workshop on Materials and Engineering Technologies for Particle Accelerator Beam Diagnostic Instruments", in Proc. 10th Int. Beam Instrumentation Conf. (IBIC'19), Pohang, Korea, Sep. 2021, pp. 16-20. [doi:10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2021-MOOB04](https://doi.org/10.18429/JACoW-IBIC2021-MOOB04).
- [5] S. H. Mirza, R. Singh, P. Forck, and H. Klingbeil, "Closed Orbit Correction at Synchrotrons for symmetric and near-symmetric Lattices", Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 22, 072804 (2019). [doi:10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.22.072804](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.22.072804).
- [6] S. H. Mirza, R. Singh, P. Forck, and B. Lorentz, "Performance of the closed Orbit Feedback Systems with spatial Model Mismatch", Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 23, 072801 (2020). [doi:10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.23.072801](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.23.072801).

9. Attachments

The summaries of the individual workshops related to Deliverable 8.3 are attached in chronological order. As various authors wrote the reports, the style varies, but the text should introduce the workshop topic and the individual talks. More information is available at the individual slides and the references therein.

ARIES-ADA Topical Workshop
Next Generation Beam Position Acquisition
And Feedback Systems
at Electron and Hadron Synchrotrons

Barcelona, Spain, November 12 - 14, 2018

INDICO-site: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/>

Workshop Summary

Editors: Peter Forck - GSI, Nicolas Hubert - SOLEIL, Ubaldo Iriso - ALBA,
Rhodri Jones - CERN, Gero Kube - DESY, Marco Lonza – Elettra,
Angel Olmos – ALBA, Guenther Rehm - DLS, and Volker Schlott – PSI

● **Organized by:**

● **Sponsored by:**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under Grant Agreement No 730871

WORKSHOP INTRODUCTION AND GOALS

The workshop is a common project between Work Packages WP8.3 and WP8.4 of the ADA-ARIES EU funded programme and its organization is shared between ALBA and CERN with some contributions by GSI.

Beam Position Monitors (BPM) and its Data Acquisition (DAQ) as well as Feedback Systems is a topic for all accelerators types. Experts from the electron and hadron synchrotron communities presented the status of their developments, learn from the other experts, discuss about the challenges common to both communities face for the next generation machines and enhance synergies between the two communities. The related discussion on common challenges was very fruitful as joint efforts can be undertaken and novel technical solutions can be adapted from the hadron to the electron synchrotron and vice versa.

The program includes specific sessions for Hadron and Electron synchrotrons, as well as plenary sessions for both communities:

Monday Nov. 12th: Hadron BPM Analog and Digital Electronics

Tuesday Nov. 13th: Orbit feedback systems for Hadron and Electron Synchrotrons

Wednesday Nov. 14th: Feedback Systems for Electron Synchrotrons

84 experts from Europe, America, Asia, and Australia participated; in particular, a large delegation from China contributed to the workshop topics. Two scientific talks were given by companies on their hard- and software developments. Due to the originally unexpected large interest in the topic, the duration of the talks was shortened to about 20 minutes to allow for discussions directly after the contribution. The contribution by two American participants were given in a remote format.

The workshop INDICO site is <https://indico.cern.ch/event/743699/> .

Monday Nov 15th		Tuesday Nov 16th		Wednesday Nov 17th	
Session 1 - HADRON BPM ANALOG ELECTRONICS		Session 3 - ORBIT FEEDBACK SYSTEMS FOR HADRON AND ELECTRON SYNCHROTRONS - PART 1		Session 5 - INSTABILITIES FEEDBACK SYSTEMS FOR ELECTRON SYNCHROTRONS	
Workshop Director: A. Marin (ALBA)					
09:00	Analogue electronics for BPMs at GSI - Performance and limitations. W. Krämer (GSI)	09:00	Overview from light source - demands, achievements, and future challenges. M. Sage (PSI)	09:00	Coupled-bunch instabilities and the Arco-Krasina principle. D. Teytelman (Duke)
10:00	Diode Orbit electronics & performance. M. Gasior (CERN)	10:00	LIBERA BPM and Closed Orbit feedback systems. A. Sardofer (Institute of Photonics and Electronics)	10:00	Longitudinal feedback systems at the lepton collider DAFNE. A. Dragone (INFN)
11:00	The SNS Ring BPM system - old and new. E. Dickson (SNS)	11:00	Fast Orbit Feedback - soft or hard real-time?. T. Tan (Australian Synchrotron)	11:00	Fast kickers for multi-bunch feedback. M. Dehler (PSI)
Coffee break		Coffee break		Coffee break	
11:30	Time multiplexing of BPM signals to avoid channel to channel variations. M. Wondol (CERN)	11:30	New BPM system and Fast Orbit Feedback for SLS 2.0 II. Kiel (PSI)	11:30	Experience on the integration of Diamond MBF-2 @ ESRF. B. Koehn (ESRF)
12:30	BPM systems at BNL. R. Mickroff (BNL)	12:30	The fast orbit correction scheme of the ESRF EBS storage ring. E. Flouves (ESRF)	12:30	Feedbacks against collective instabilities at MAX IV. F. Cullnan (MAX IV)
13:30	Performance of the new Logarithmic Amplifier based Electronics for the CERN SPS. T. Ilgner (CERN)	13:30	The new ASTRID2 Fast Orbit Feedback system. J.S. Nelson (SLAC)	13:30	New Spring-8 Bunch-by-Bunch Feedback Processor for hybrid filling. T. Nakamura (Spring-8)
14:30	The design & progress of bunch by bunch measurement system for HAF. M. Li (IMP)	14:30	The Petra 3 fast orbit feedback system. H. Duhren (DESY)	14:30	Single bunch instabilities with transverse feedback at Diamond Light Source. E. Rokkovi-Plata (CERN)
LUNCH		LUNCH		LUNCH	
Session 2 - HADRON BPM DIGITAL ELECTRONICS & DAQ		Session 4 - ORBIT FEEDBACK SYSTEMS FOR HADRON AND ELECTRON SYNCHROTRONS - PART 2		Session 6 - ORBIT FEEDBACK TOOLS FOR ELECTRON SYNCHROTRONS	
14:30	Data transmission & digitization - what is state of the art today?. M. Basso Marin (CERN)	14:30	LHC orbit feedback - architecture & operational experience. J. Weinger (CERN)	14:30	Suppression of the injection perturbation using feed-forward techniques. E. Flouves (ESRF)
15:30	Digital electronics & DAQ for IR, algorithms for position calculations and achievable resolution. A. Reiter (GSI)	15:30	Robustness considerations for a fast orbit feedback at hadron synchrotrons. S. Mirza-Sadeghi	15:30	New corrector power supplies for SLS / SLS-2.0 II. Juckle (PSI)
16:30	A next generation digital BPM system for the LHC. A. Soccadi (CERN)	16:30	BPM Data Acquisition and Orbit Feedback at BNL. A. Mariani (BNL)	16:30	Closing remarks. A. Cimoz (ALBA)
Coffee break		Coffee break		Coffee break	
16:30	Digital BPM development for HEPS project. S. Wei (IHEP)	16:30	The NSLS-II BPM system. D. Pacheco (BNL)		
17:30	Bunch-by-Bunch position measurement for the CERN-PS: coping with RF-gymnastics. J. Rebernik (CERN)	17:30	BPM and Orbit Feedback System for ALS Upgrade. G. Partemann (ALS)		
18:30	BPM electronics and orbit feedback system at Sirius. D. Tavares (LBNL)				
20:00 - Bus from Hotel to restaurant		20:30 - Workshop Dinner			

Workshop agenda

● **Session 1 - HADRON BPM ANALOG ELECTRONICS (Rhodri Jones - CERN)**

Analogue electronics for BPMs at GSI - Performance and limitations

Winfried Krämer, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

For the GSI proton LINAC BPMs a new pre-amplifier is under development matched to the 325 MHz acceleration frequency. For the low energy and low current storage ring CRYRING the amplifier is optimized for low signals and comprises a high impedance input. The development for the high current ion synchrotrons and transport lines at GSI was realized in collaboration with industry. The three amplifier designs were presented:

- **Phase matched amplifier** for time of flight measurements. This has a bandwidth from 325 MHz to 3.25 GHz, a gain from 0 dB to 40 dB (in 10dB steps) and phase matching delay lines to achieve 0.1° phase accuracy at 325 MHz.
- **Low noise amplifier for CRYRING:** The main features include a bandwidth from 10 kHz to 40 MHz, a near constant gain (40 dB or 60 dB +/- 0.05 dB) over the entire range, an input/output impedance of 1 MΩ / 50 Ω and an equivalent input noise of only 2.3 nV / \sqrt{Hz} . A BPM linked to such an amplifier was shown to be much better than an ICT for measuring the intensity of low current (10nA) beams.
- **High dynamic range (110 dB) 50 Ω amplifier/attenuator** whose main features include a selectable gain in the range -50 dB to 60 dB (10 dB steps), a bandwidth from 40 kHz to 55 MHz and an equivalent input noise of 1.6 nV / \sqrt{Hz} .

Diode Orbit Electronics

Marek Gasior, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

A new concept for high-resolution position measurement based on compensated diode detectors was presented. In this system the forward voltage across the diodes, which would otherwise introduce a significant position error, is compensated using two operational amplifiers. Such a system has been constructed for use in the embedded collimator BPMs of the LHC and for the directional BPMs near the LHC interaction points. While the system works very well for the centred beams in the collimators, reaching sub-micron resolution, it is a challenge to make it work as a normal beam position system. For non-centred beams, the limited linear dynamic range of the detector leads to a dependence of the measured position on the signal amplitude. This can be mitigated by the use of variable gain amplifiers, but complicates the system and still results in errors some two orders of magnitude larger than the system resolution. The design also includes cross-bar switching to eliminate systematic gain and offset errors in the parallel processing chains used for opposite electrodes.

SNS Ring BPM System – Old and New

Richard Dickson, ORNL, Oak Ridge, USA

The main motivation to move to a new system was obsolescence of hardware and software, the limitation of 1Hz acquisition (60Hz required) and an increased dynamic range from the original 5×10^{10} - 2×10^{14} to the extended 6×10^9 - 6×10^{14} protons per pulse. A custom analogue front-end is built, but the DAQ solution was chosen to be an industrial platform due to the limited availability of experienced digital engineers - NI PXI system (NI PXIe-8880 CPU, NI PXIe-7971 FPGA, NI 5751B ADC). Two jitter reduction algorithms were presented – one using linear interpolation to combat phase slip of the RF frequency with respect to a free running ADC, and one to cope with jitter on the acquisition trigger. The final application software now displays turn-by-turn position, orbit, bunch centroid and peak phase, and position evolution within a given turn.

BPM Signal Processing using Time-Multiplexed Electrode Signals

Manfred Wendt, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

The presentation was focussed on techniques for minimising time varying asymmetries between electrode acquisition channels that result in uncontrollable position offsets – one of the major limitation of any BPM system's performance. The main emphasis was on single channel receivers using time-multiplexing of the input signals. Such systems eliminate asymmetries by design, but only work for beams where the time between bunches is long compared to the bunch signal. The case of the LHC was cited as an example with 1 ns bunch length and a spacing of 25 ns. However, it was pointed out that this could also work for picosecond electron bunches spaced by a few nanoseconds. The components needed for such a scheme are a high isolation power combiner and a delay line filter (comb band-pass filter). Examples of both, adapted to a 500 MHz operating frequency, were presented.

BPM Systems at Brookhaven National Laboratory

Rob Michnoff, BNL, Brookhaven, USA

The presentation gave an insight into the many BPM systems developed for the various accelerators at BNL. Most of these are now based on an in-house designed V301 VME DAQ module. Its main features include a Xilinx Zynq gate array running Linux in its Arm processor (bootable from an on-board microSD card), 400 MSPS 14-bit ADCs, 1GB DDR3 memory, and 2 ethernet connections, one for controls communication and the other for custom use (e.g. high speed position distribution). This can be adapted to a variety of acquisition techniques – oversampling, undersampling and single sample on bunch peak. In addition, it includes an RF section with selectable gain and filtering stages, which can be adapted to work with ion, proton and electron beams.

Performance of the Log Amp based Electronics developed for the SPS at CERN

Thierry Bogey, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

The choice of technology was driven by the desire to cover a large dynamic range without gain switching, minimising the complexity of the gain setting per beam type and the associated calibration factors. It was shown that a single log-amp (Analog Devices ADL5519 dual-channel logarithmic amplifier) could only provide a linear response over a dynamic range of 40 dB, which was not sufficient. Three parallel channels, spaced by 20dB, have therefore been implemented to cover a total dynamic range of 70dB. Despite residing in the same IC package, the two log-amps within the ADL5519 were shown to have gains that could be mismatched by a few %, leading to intensity dependent position drifts. This problem is overcome by acquiring the channels individually rather than using the in-chip difference output. In this way each channel can be calibrated and corrected. As all three gain stages are acquired in parallel the optimised choice of gain can be made in the processing FPGA or software layer. Use of a hairpin band-pass filter to stretch the response for single bunches was also presented.

The design & progress of the bunch-by-bunch measurement system for HIAF

Min Li, IMP, Lanzhou, China

The presentation gave an overview of the HIAF facility, with its ion Linac, booster ring, fragment separator and spectrometer ring. The booster ring contains 39 elliptical, ceramic, diagonally cut BPMs, based on a GSI design, that will be linked to a system that needs to provide 10 kHz data for orbit feedback. To implement the fast orbit feedback three data communication protocols have been studied: reflective memory, remote direct memory access and commercial (NI) protocols. Two possible architectures for the HIAF closed orbit feedback system were then presented. The first based on Libera Hadron, similar to what is being implemented for GSI, and the second on a commercial DAQ system (NI or MicroTCA). It was commented that the physics-driven MicroTCA.4 standards could be of interest because of its flexibility, modularity, redundancy in key components, and advanced crate management system, with Rapid I/O the preferred choice for backplane communication.

- **Session 2 - HADRON BPM DIGITAL ELECTRONICS & DAQ (P. Forck)**

Data transmission & digitalization – What is state-of-the-art today?

Manoel Barros Marin, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

For the long term perspective of LHC a new BPM system must be implemented. In this contribution the main focus is related to ADC chip and digital data transmission. For the existing installation those components

were developed at CERN in connection with groups from the high energy physics detector. This included a radiation hard layout for some components installed in the tunnel. The properties of the used AD41240 are given and the application of the LHC BPM amplitude-to-time conversion chain is depicted. For LHC run 3 (starting in 2021 after the long shutdown LS2) the usage of COTS ADCs is foreseen for any new installations. An optical data link realization is discussed.

Digital Electronics & DAQ for FAIR - Algorithms for position calculation and achievable resolution

Andreas Reiter, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

The digital signal processing of the BPMs at GSI's SIS18 and for FAIR was presented. The bunch length at those synchrotrons and storage rings ranges from 50 ns to some 1 μ s and, after broadband amplification the digitalization rate is 125 or 250 MSa/s. Different methods for the digital treatment of such oversampled bunches were discussed and compared concerning their accuracy and numerical stability: The 'classical' method comprises the integration of the bunch-signal, which requires firstly the generation of a window to distinguish between the bunch signal and the pause to enable an adequate baseline reconstruction as the second step followed by a difference-of-sum position calculation. The usage of the signal power, i.e. the square of the electrode followed by the position proportional difference calculation, is usage as a second method. As a novel alternative, a least-square fit of opposite plate signals was realized: The slope of the curve is related to the beam position. The achievable properties concerning resolution, noise and offset immunity of the three methods are compared in detail. The advantages of the latter methods were clearly demonstrated. One advantage is that a bunch recognition isn't required and closed orbit determination can be done with a long, user-defined time window. As an 'exotic' application a position reading even for dc-beams could be achieved by using the 'Schottky-like' signals.

A next generation digital BPM system for the LHC

Andrea Boccardi, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

At present the BPM position evaluation proceeds via time-multiplexed signal chain was designed more than 20 years ago (see the talk by M. Wendt during this workshop): The four electrode signals are individually delayed and transmitted via one cable with the advantage of systematic drift compensation. The general properties of several position evaluation algorithms (Delta-over-sum, linear displacement dependence and rms power evaluation) are compared. The requirements of the ADC resolution for those algorithms are given e.g. for nominal LHC currents with 10^{10} protons/bunch an 9.6 effective bit ADC delivers about 0.1 mm resolution for the broadband signal. These results are weight in terms of accuracy for an interlock generation. The foreseen hardware design (ADC and FPGA) is shown.

Brief Introduction to the Digital BPM development for HEPS project

Sun Jun-Wei, IHEP, Beijing, China

For the High Energy Photon Source HEPS in total 693 BPM locations are planned with 576 stations in the 1300 m long storage ring. The design criteria for the BPM digital electronics and the decision using home-made boards were discussed. The hardware realization of the analogue and digital front-end were shown and test results are shown. Beam-based tests will be done at existing BEPCII facility; first results are promising. As a form-factor μ TCA4.0 is realized. The suitable algorithms were simulated in Matlab extensively and their

firmware is now implemented. Some optimizations for the hardware remains, e.g. methods related to the temperature influence and the calibration method have to be implemented.

Bunch-by-Bunch position measurement for the CERN-PS: coping with RF-gymnastics *Jeroen Bellemann, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland*

The technical layout of the CERN PS system comprises of 43 BPMs for trajectory determination was discussed in detail. The analogue signal chain comprises of hybrids to generate difference and sum followed by variable gain amplifiers. Signals are digitized by 125 MSa/s ADCs on a commercially produced cPCI crate-based board. The creation of windows for the bunch-synchronous signal integration is locked to the revolution frequency by a Numerical Controlled Oscillator PLL and a look-up table for a possible variation of the relative phase realized on an FPGA basis. The bunch repetition frequency as a higher harmonics of the revolution is generated by this cycle- and time-dependent look-up table. The technical system realization was discussed in detail and the properties were demonstrated with relevant examples. As several steps of bunch merging and splitting are performed during the PS cycle, the system flexibility was discussed and it was shown that a pause-free trajectory display can be achieved. The large flexibility of the chosen digital processing was demonstrated for the system which works in a stable manner since several years in particular for the display during the bunch gymnastics within the PS cycle.

BPM Electronics and Orbit Feedback Systems at SIRIUS

Daniel Tavares, LNLS Sirius, Campinas, Brazil

The requirement of the BPM system for the Brazilian Synchrotron Light Source was presented for turn-by-turn and closed orbit determination in terms of resolution and stability. The main part of the contribution was attributed to the hardware realization. In contrary to many other light sources, the electronics is partly home-made and based on the design published at an open hardware repositories and the related codes are available at: <http://github.com/lnls-dig> and <https://www.ohwr.org/projects/afc>. The layout and the achieved properties of the analogue front-end are discussed. Generally, the design of the digital components is based on μ TCA4.0 carrier boards and FMC extensions using open hardware and commercial products. The digital processing is based on a standard digital radio receiver method. A modified difference-of-sum algorithm is used to provide higher resolution for the typical booster BPM electrode orientation. The achievements concerning resolution and stability obtained at a test bench were presented and the solution of commissioning problems was discussed. The design considerations of the fast Closed Orbit Feedback were given; the commissioning of the entire system is expected for spring 2019. Generally, the experiences using open hardware design and its production were quite positive.

- **Session 3 - ORBIT FEEDBACK SYSTEMS FOR HADRON AND ELECTRON SYNCHROTRONS - PART 1 (N. Hubert, G. Kube)**

Overview from light source – demands, achievements, and future challenges

Micheal Böge, PSI, Villigen, Switzerland

LIBERA BPM and Closed Orbit feedback systems

Ales Bardorfer, Instrumentation Technologies, Solkan, Slovenia

Fast Orbit Feedback - soft or hard real-time?

Eugene Tan, AS-ANSTO, Clayton, Australia

The three talks cover the important topic of Closed Orbit Feedback in a comparable manner. The demands and requirements for the Beam Position Monitor (BPMs) and Orbits Feedback (OFB) systems for future low emittance light sources are already almost fulfilled on current machines, in term of resolution and stability. Nevertheless, they are still ways for improvements:

- BPM better resolution in turn by turn for better optics measurement.
- BPM higher bandwidth and sampling rate could provide bunch by bunch position measurements.
- Increase (in frequency) the fast orbit feedback 0 dB point. This is not so much the perturbations at higher frequencies that need to be suppressed, as the perturbations at low frequency that could be damped higher with this increase.
- Integrate in the FOFB more actuators (skew quads, quads...) and sensors (beam size monitors, photon BPMs...) for coupling, lifetime and optic control at higher rate.

Currently the main limitation to increase the FOFB bandwidth (0 dB point) is generally the latency in the feedback loop. This latency comes from 2 main contributions: BPM filtering (group delay) and magnet bandwidth (except for air coil correctors) whereas the FOFB computation contribution is rather small (few μ s) thanks to the massive parallelism provided by FPGAs or GPUs.

AS-ANSTO demonstrates the viability of a FOFB processing, based on real-time Linux on COTS PCs. The main drawback is the additional processing delay that reduces the bandwidth. Nevertheless, it is a way to develop rapidly a solution when you miss specialized FPGA developers.

New BPM system and Fast Orbit Feedback for SLS 2.0

Boris Keil, PSI, Villigen, Switzerland

Boris Keil (PSI) reported about the SLS-2 upgrade and the renewal of the RF BPM and fast orbit feedback system. Specifications for this new system are a position noise of < 50 nm (rms @ BW 1 kHz) resp. < 1 μ m (rms @ BW 0.5 MHz) and a position drift (electronics only) of < 100 nm/hour, all values taken at nominal beam current. In order to make the BPM electronics simpler, cheaper and more performant, it is planned to use latest technologies (Xilinx Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC and JESD204B ADCs with multi-gigabit link), using a newly developed BPM specific housing with hot pluggable BPM RF front-end/ADC modules. In 2017 the development of the new "DBPM3" BPM platform started which shall have much lower hardware complexity and points of failure compared to the former DBPM systems. SLS-2 will require 31 DPPM3 units (incl. spares) for the RF BPM system with 3 BPMs per unit, and 27 units for the FOFB with 16 SFPs per unit. For the new FOFB system a tree topology will be used with centralized feedback algorithm.

The fast orbit correction scheme of the ESRF EBS storage ring

Eric Plouviez, ESRF, Grenoble, France

Eric Plouviez (ESRF) reported about the new fast orbit correction scheme of the ESRF EBS storage ring. Each new EBS Hybrid MBA cell (in total 32 cells) includes 10 BPMs (6 equipped with Libera Brilliance and fast outputs, 4 with Libera Sparks without fast outputs) and 9 correctors (3 fast correctors @ 500Hz BW and 6 slow correctors embedded in the sextupoles). He demonstrated that small and fast orbit distortions without DC component can be corrected with the subgroup of $32 \times 6 = 192$ BPMs and $32 \times 3 = 96$ correctors without spoiling the correction quality such that in principle a reuse of the former orbit correction system is possible. The remaining 128 BPMs equipped with Libera Sparks and the 192 slow correctors will be used for slow orbit control such that the entire orbit control system will consist of a hybrid slow/fast configuration. Tests performed at the present ESRF storage ring with only 5 BPMs and 2 correctors per cell for fast corrections (and 7 BPMs/ 3 correctors per cell for slow corrections) indicate a perturbation on the horizontal beam position which could be identified as leaking of the septum pulse and compensated by a feed forward correction.

The new ASTRID2 Fast Orbit Feedback system

Jørgen S. Nielsen, ISA, Aarhus, Denmark

Jørgen S. Nielsen (ISA, Aarhus University) presented the new ASTRID2 fast orbit feedback system. The ring has 24 BPMs equipped with Libera Electron, 12 HV window frame correctors, and additional 12 H correctors. Up to now only a Labview-based slow orbit feedback was implemented based on the 12 HV correctors, and a lot of orbit disturbances could be observed in the beam spectrum (caused by several reasons). A new cheap and simple fast orbit feedback system was installed based on a standard PC running with the Labview real-time environment and performing the orbit calculations. Input data are the 10 kHz FA data of the Liberases, and for the output the digital values from a FPGA enabled DAQ card are fed to 4 DAC chips via SPI-like lines. Two software loops are in operation, one for high priority (10 kHz) and one for low priority (1-10 Hz), data are transferred between the loops via real time FIFOs. Based on this setup a clear improvement was observed in the beam spectrum below 100 Hz.

Digital Electronics & DAQ for FAIR - Algorithms for position calculation and achievable resolution The Petra 3 fast orbit feedback system

Hans-Thomas Duhme, DESY, Hamburg, Germany

Hans-Thomas Duhme (DESY) gave an overview over the PETRA-III fast orbit feedback system which is successfully in operation since the machine commissioning in 2009. Main tasks are to stabilize the orbit to $\pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ in the vertical plane over 24 h, the damping of orbit distortions from DC up to 200 Hz, the compensation of 50 Hz disturbances and higher harmonics, a feed forward during injection, and the interaction with the slow orbit control and beamline via the control system. The system architecture is based on star topology; it processes turn-by-turn data from 246 BPMs to the power supplies while using a custom-made TbT data output from Libera Brilliances. The correctors consist of air coils mounted over stainless steel chambers and powered by fully digital current source power supplies. The system has no frequency gap, the reference orbit of the feedback is determined by slow orbit corrections, and the DC current of the fast correctors is removed by transferring it to the slow corrector magnets. The 3dB cut-off frequency is 390 Hz, however the system is bandwidth limited by filters to 150-200 Hz for better noise performance. Higher frequencies are processed with 50 Hz compensation and adaptive injection feed forward.

- **Session 4 - ORBIT FEEDBACK SYSTEMS FOR HADRON AND ELECTRON SYNCHROTRONS - PART 2 (G. Rehm, V. Schlott)**

LHC orbit feedback – architecture & operational experience

Jörg Wenniger, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

Jörg Wenniger presented a talk providing the link bridge for Orbit FB on Hadron synchrotrons and light sources. He emphasized the need for orbit control in hadron machines to be more connected to collimation systems and interaction points. Due to the superconducting nature of many magnets, LHC is inherently a slow machine, so orbit feedback aims a close loop BW of 0.1-1 Hz. A commercial PC server acts as the controller for all 2000 monitors and 1100 actuators, at an update rate of 25Hz. Monitors are affected by some systematic errors which can be removed by calibration, and mainly temperature drift of 20-50um.

Optics are corrected by AC excitation and BPM turn-by-turn data. Response matrices for orbit feedback are pre-calculated from a model, and inverted using SVD with clipping of higher singular values. Stability is adequate for achieving good collisions, however, even small earthquakes or large building activity push the OFB to its limits. For the future, a faster OFB (~30Hz BW) is under consideration.

Robustness considerations for a fast orbit feedback at hadron synchrotrons

Sajjad Mirza, GSI, Darmstadt, Germany

Sajjad presented on considerations and first experiments for Closed Orbit FB at FAIR, where OFB is required due to the multitude of fast cycles for acceleration of different ion species. Disturbance come not only from hysteresis errors in magnets, but also through EMI due to very thin walled chambers. For the Orbit FB during the ramp, deliberate misfit of the actual ORM and the factual ORM of the machine have been considered. Sajjad went on to compare approaches of harmonic correction using Fourier decomposition with singular value decomposition, and highlighted the weakness in human interpretation in the SVD approach. He found that due to the frequent symmetry in ORMs, they can be expressed as circulant matrices, which comes with beneficial effects for decomposition. Even when the lattice is not fully symmetric, it can be shown that a close circulant matrix can still be used as a proxy, and might have certain advantages. Finally, light was cast at model mismatch due to betatron tune shift, and a methodology to assess this was drawn out. This was concluded with a comparison of prediction and experiment at COSY.

BPM Data Acquisition and Orbit Feedback at BNL

Al Marusic, BNL, Brookhaven, USA

Al provided an entertaining talk with lots of anecdotes from RHIC, where OFB was only introduced during the 11th year of operation. Orbit in RHIC is measured at 167 locations, but 117 locations are considered enough for a sufficient accurate orbit determination. Other BPMs are for special purposes and for redundancy. Consequently, there are 117 corrector magnets. Using OFB, the beam can be steered to desired orbits, and these are easily programmable, including ramps. Updates of the orbit progress slowly, with individual changes taking up to 1 second to complete.

Actual offsets of BPMs to quads were measured at installation and found to be RMS ~0.5mm. Later these are re-measured using Beam Based Alignment.

The NSLS-II BPM system

Danny Padrazo, BNL, Brookhaven, USA

Although the performance of the present NSLS-II BPM system fulfills the original (and present) specifications / requirements:

- 1 μm (rms) turn-by-turn resolution
- 200 nm (rms) resolution @ the fast orbit feedback sampling rate of 10 kHz
- 200 nm / 8 hrs (@ 10 kHz) long term stability

hardware obsolescence of 9+ years old technology as well as a number of reliability issues and short-comings such as poor network performance and inconvenience with non-standardized operating system and software development environment motivates a presently ongoing BPM electronics upgrade program at NSLS-II.

The NSLS-II BPM electronics upgrade comprises a new digital front end unit called zDFE and a new RF front end called AFE. The major improvements and new / advanced features of the zDFE are:

- Hard dual-core ARM A9 processor with > 500 Mbit/s throughput (25 x performance increase as compared to the present NSLS-II BPM system)
- Runs standard Debian-7 based Linux operating system and provides embedded IOC
- DMA Kernel driver for large waveform access (up to 300 Mbyte)
- Standardized DFE and SW development platform (similar to standard Linux server) allows the inclusion of multiple sub-systems such as RFBPMs, bunch-by-bunch BPMs, X-ray BPMs, controller for fast orbit feedback etc.
- Advanced / improved FPGA resources for digital signal processing may even support bunch-by-bunch position calculation
- Integrated 10 Gbps transceivers allows interfacing of fast (500 MSPS) ADCs

Prototype tests of the new zDFE BPM module with beam have shown that the NSLS-II performance requirements (see above) can be fulfilled.

A number of upgrade considerations for the BPM analog frontend (zAFE) are mainly focusing on noise reduction and improvement of the long-term stability. Features like active temperature control to 1°C, 2-way diagonal switching of RF signals from the pick-ups (A/C, B/D) using a mobile cell RF switch (external switch box for prototype beam tests in collaboration with the Brazilian LS) were applied, while the successful implementation of a (out-of-band) pilot tone was prevented by the temperature dependent pass-band response of the existing SAW filters on the present RFBPM AFE. Beam tests (over 24 hours) show that the new AFE features improves the position resolution from presently 130 nm (rms) to < 20 nm (rms) with the main noise reduction (PSD plot) below 1 kHz (further averaged display on the control room panel show even 2 nm BPM position resolution for the operators indicating the performance level and BPM system health).

In addition to upgrading the present NSLS-II BPM electronics (turn-by-turn and orbit feedback modes), a bunch-by-bunch zAFE is under consideration utilizing improved ADC technology (e.g. 14/16 bit ADCs like ADS54J66 or ADS54J69 from Texas Instruments) and latest advances in FPGA technology (e.g. 1st or 2nd generation Xilinx RFSoc FPGAs with 8 channel, 12 bit or 14 bit, 4 or 5 Gsps). First prototype hardware tests with beam (325 mA, 1000 bunches) show very promising results: ~ 5 μm (rms) bunch-by-bunch and ~ 0.6 μm (rms) turn-by-turn position resolution.

BPM and Orbit Feedback System for ALS Upgrade

Gregory Portmann, ALS, Berkeley, USA

ALS-U beam parameters and stability goals define the BPM requirements:

- different fill pattern (single to multi-bunch) determine the full dynamic range
- beam stability needs to be provided over a large frequency range, translating into 200 nm (rms) position resolution (and drift) from a few days to 10 kHz

ALS-U will need 192 BPMs in the storage ring (16 per sector), 72 BPMs in the accumulator ring (6 per sector) and ~ 20 BPMs in the transfer lines. The ALS BPM development team (Gregory Portmann, Eric Norum, Jonah Weber, Mike Chin and Rick Lellinger) is closely collaborating with the NSLS-II BPM experts and uses the NSLS digital front end (DFE), while a number of modifications / optimizations were made to the analog front end (AFE) regarding the ALS parameters.

- pilot tone generation has been put on a separate system
- each analog chain has its separate power regulation
- reference clock generation comes from the FPGA
- increased number of temperature monitors (8 instead of 2)
- monitoring voltages and currents for 3 supplies
- the backside of the PCB is thermally connected to the case
- each DAT is individually controlled
- SAW band-pass filters have been replaced by thermally more stable ceramic filters

For online calibration and drift compensation of the ALS BPM electronics a pilot tone at ± 2 MHz from the 500 MHz BPM carrier signal has been fed in through a combiner stage in the ALS tunnel (to improve the temperature stability). However, the ALS BPM team has found out that this correction mechanism suffers from a strong temperature dependency of the SAW filter pass band behavior, resulting in different transfer function for the RF carrier and the pilot tone. Comparative studies of ceramic filters to the original SAW filter indicate that a mono-block ceramic filter (from CTS) shows the best (temperature) behavior, leading to this important design change in the AFE.

While the NSLS-II digital front end board (DFE) could be taken over without any hardware modifications, the firmware and EPICS software was changed / adapted completely for the ALS BPM system. BPM noise floor measurements (one button signal was split four ways to the BPM inputs) show that the ALS BPM electronics remains below the specified 200 nm (rms) noise floor between 0.4 to 5 kHz, with a very efficient pilot tone noise correction up to 1 kHz (only 75 nm rms noise). This new BPM electronics performance will thus strongly improve the ALS fast orbit feedback system, where most of the beam disturbances occur between 10 and 200 Hz (as shown in an integrated PSD plot). The long term drift (over days) is strongly improved from presently 8 – 10 μm to 0.2 μm with pilot tone compensation. Turn-by-turn resolution (important for beam commissioning and beam optics studies) is below 1 μm (rms) at 500 mA multi-bunch filling and below 10 μm for low bunch charges (beam currents during injection studies and commissioning).

An “expert panel” was presented, which allows BPM health monitoring and maintenance from the control room. It monitors all relevant system parameters (e.g. temperatures, voltages and clock signals) and allows switching to the pilot tone for diagnostic checks of BPM electronics.

For the APS-U, the following (main) features (wish list) should be implemented in a new BPM system:

- Faster ADCs (> 125 MHz sampling rate or 77 samples per storage ring turn)

- Improved components like e.g.: band-pass filters, DAT and amplifiers
- Cleaner pilot tone (mainly above 1 kHz)
- 4 channel ADCs

Plans were shown to stepwise improve the orbit stability at ALS by upgrading the fast orbit feedback (FOFB) with a large number of the new ALS BPM electronics (making the transition in 2019 from Bergoz electronics), new CAEN power supply controllers (CAEN fast-PS-Series operating at 10 kHz) and implementing the ALS Cell Controller for the FOFB communication. With the replacement of the Al vacuum chambers by higher bandwidth stainless steel chambers at the location of the fast correctors, a closed loop bandwidth of 500 – 1000 Hz is anticipated.

- **Session 5 - INSTABILITIES FEEDBACK SYSTEMS FOR ELECTRON SYNCHROTRONS
(U. Iriso, M. Lonza)**

After a general instruction to a bunch-by-bunch feedback, the first part of the session characterized by speakers with long experience in the field of multi-bunch feedback systems, the second part was dedicated to new implementations and recent machine physics studies using feedback systems.

Coupled-bunch Instabilities and the Anna Karenina Principle

Dmitry Teytelman, Dimtel, San Jose, USA

Dimitry showed us how under proper feedback control, all storage rings look more or less alike. But after his presentation, we saw that each accelerator presents unique set of challenges for feedback stabilization. The frequency spectra of machines with properly working feedback systems shows clean notches at the horizontal and vertical planes. But each small undamped instability needs its own special treatment, and Dmitry went through a variety of (exotic) instabilities seen by different accelerators: from ion instabilities (Bessy-II) to resistive wall resonances produced only at certain In-Vacuum Undulators gaps (Australian and Aichi Light Sources), or the coupling between longitudinal and transverse planes (ANKA). In order to properly damp all instabilities, feedback systems need first to become an efficient tool to diagnose them and understand their origin. For future machines, it was mentioned that new light sources and colliders are going become more and more sensitive to residual dipole motion in the transverse plane, low-noise techniques in RF front end and digitizer design are required.

Longitudinal feedback systems at the lepton collider DAFNE

Alessandro Drago, INFN Frascati, Italy

Alessandro Drago summarized the specifications for a longitudinal feedback system. One topic is the requirements for the front-end electronics to acquire for each bunch the longitudinal oscillations respect to the synchronous phase (phase detector). Using powerful models of FPGA, it was possible to implement very compact version of feedback systems in the digital/analog part of the back-end. While for the acting device, cavity kickers are preferred with respect to stripline-type-kickers to avoid instabilities.

Fast kickers for Multi-Bunch Feedbacks

Micha Dehler, PSI, Villigen, Switzerland

Kickers in transverse multi-bunch feedbacks are stripline-type, with the goal of producing strong and homogenous kicks, with load broad-band impedance and negligible contributions from HOMs. This presentation went through the main concepts to achieve these goals. In particular, maximizing the stripline kick (or the stripline shunt impedance) consists on choosing the appropriate shape and location of the electrodes. Nevertheless, even though electrodes are relatively well thermally isolated, there have been some cases where the beam power distribution has damaged the electrodes due to HOM heating (Diamond and Petra-III, the latter including water cooling system in the electrodes).

Experience on the integration of Diamond MBF-2 @ ESRF

Benoît Roche, ESRF, Grenoble, France

Benoît Roche presented the new ESRF bunch-by-bunch digital processor based on a Diamond Light Source design. At ESRF multi-bunch feedbacks are not used during user operation but only in particular cases to increase the maximum current both in multi and single bunch mode. In the future, they plan to use the feedbacks and their diagnostic capabilities to speed up the commissioning of the accelerator after the forthcoming upgrade (ESRF-EBS). The new processor is based on a TCA platform and commercial boards with software and firmware developed by Diamond. After a smooth work of integration into the ESRF control system, the commissioning with beam has been fast and successful.

Feedbacks against collective instabilities at MAX-IV

Francis Cullinan - MAX-IV, Lund, Sweden

MAX-IV features two storage rings at 1.5 and 3 GeV, both of them equipped with longitudinal and transverse bunch-by-bunch feedback systems employing the hardware from company Dimtel. The interaction between harmonic cavities used for bunch lengthening and the feedbacks is quite challenging due to the effect on the synchrotron frequency and energy spread. The talk presented the studies and experience gained in operating them at the same time. Mode-0 and quadrupole instabilities were also discussed as well as the remedies adopted to control them.

New SPring-8 Bunch-by-Bunch Feedback Processor for hybrid filling

Takeshi Nakamura, Spring-8, Hyogo, Japan

The talk was another example of sharing a common project among different laboratories, being a development carried out by Spring-8 in collaboration with SOLEIL and PLS. Takeshi Nakamura presented a different approach of implementing the feedback processor based on an original idea aimed at solving the problem of managing storage-ring hybrid fillings with single high-charge bunches. The processor features multiple ADCs dedicated to different bunches and a digital selector to recombine the calculated digital kick signals. The presentation also included other interesting approaches for kick pulse-length stretching, multiple BPMs feedback, beam size feedback control and head-tail feedback for single bunch instabilities.

Single bunch instabilities with transverse feedback at Diamond Light Source (*Andreas E. Eirini Koukovini-Platia, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland*)

Eirini Koukovini-Platia presented a study carried out at the Diamond Light Source on single bunch instabilities. The multi-bunch feedback system has been used as a powerful instrument to perform machine physics studies thanks to the built-in diagnostic functionalities implemented in its firmware. The instability current threshold in single bunch has been measured in different conditions of chromaticity and feedback settings. Thanks to this studies, with the use of the feedbacks it is now possible to store twice the single bunch current with the same chromaticity, which is particularly useful during user operations in hybrid filling mode.

- **Session 6 - ORBIT FEEDBACK TOOLS FOR ELECTRON SYNCHROTRONS (A. Olmos)**

Suppression of the injection perturbations using feed-forward techniques

Eric Plouviez, ESRF, Grenoble, France

The recent top up operation at the ESRF showed up the interest to cope the beam position perturbations due to the injection system. Eric Plouviez showed that the position oscillations are due to the none perfect closing of the kickers bump (sextupoles) and some leakage of the septum field. Orbit and Instability feedback systems are limited because of their bandwidth, but correctors bandwidth (500Hz) is enough to correct such perturbation. The use of feedforward techniques allows to get profit of the higher correctors bandwidth and acts more efficiently over the correctors strength in order to reduce the effect of the septum leakage. The speaker explained that the effect of the sextupoles in the bump is being addressed by passive cancellation (shaping the kickers filed and adding an octupole to the bump) and active correction with a shaker plus a stripline.

New corrector power supplies for SLS / SLS-2.0

Hans Jaeckle, PSI, Villigen, Switzerland

Hans Jaeckle started his contribution doing a review about power supplies, their main components, current measurement methods and their principle of operation. Then he jumped into the different generations of power supplies controllers @ PSI, analyzing the design of the controllers based on the nature of the signal to control (strength and bandwidth) and the noise and ripples sources to face. Finally, he showed the different types of power supplies expected for SLS2 machine and commented about the design process and constrains for the new power supplies, explaining in detail the plan of building a power supply prototype.

ARIES-ADA Topical Workshop

Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources

DEELS 2019

Online Workshop, June 3rd to 5th, 2019

INDICO-site: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/789811/>

Workshop Summary

Editors: Ubaldo Iriso – ALBA-CELLS, Benoît Roche – ESRF

Organised by:

Sponsored by:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under Grant Agreement No 730871

DEELS 2019: Workshop introduction and goals

During the last 6 years, the Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources meet together in a yearly workshop called DEELS to discuss common problems, share new developments, and enhance synergies between different facilities. Funded by ARIES, this year the workshop was extended to colleagues from Light Sources from all around the world (from Asia to America) which is an extension compared to the previous workshops. In total 59 people from 20 institutions and two commercial company attended. The workshop INDOCI-site is <https://indico.cern.ch/event/789811/>. In total 26 talks took place during one full and two half days. The community could take the opportunity to see the installation of the Extremely Brilliant Source (EBS): the upgrade of the ESRF.

The workshop was held from 3-5 June 2019 at the ESRF (Grenoble, France). Diagnostics for particle accelerators is a wide topic addressing different specialties: from analog and digital electronics, to x-ray optics, etc. Some speakers gave a general review of all diagnostics in their institute, especially in the ones where the installation of a 4th generation light source is foreseen or on-going. In particular, the EBS, the upgrade project in APS and SLS, and two projects of new 4th generation light sources in Russia and in China (HEPS) were presented.

Topic 1: BPMs and related electronics

During the workshop, multiple projects of new electronics developments for Beam Position Monitors (BPM) were presented. Those new developments are motivated by two main reasons: first, the recent progresses in FPGA chips open new possibilities for BPM measurement and orbit feedback. On the other hand, the ultra-low emittance beam expected with the 4th generation light sources increases the requirement for better sensitive BPM electronics, in order to achieve better beam stability. The platform currently developed by Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste focuses on the modularity of the platform and will use the so-called “pilot-tone” scheme in order to perform calibration of the analog front-end and cable transmission drifts. HEPS, SSRF and the future Russian Light Source from Kurchatov Institute are using high performances FPGA and Analog to Digital Converters to achieve bunch-by-bunch and turn by turn measurements.

Concerning BPM measurement precision and accuracy, some presentations focused on sources of error, together with proposed solutions to increase BPM performances. A. Nosych from ALBA presented a tool called “*BPMLab*” (available for all labs) to compute the deviation from the linear response of a BPM block. This tool is able to provide polynomials in order to correct the reading of a BPM to compensate for non-linearities. B. Roche from ESRF and G. Rehm from Diamond talked about the so-called Lambertson method to estimate the difference in electrodes sensitivities with a RF transmission calibration measurement. Concerning the hardware B. Repic (iTech) talked about his finding that a low-pass filter widely used in their products is the reason for electrical noise increase in their analog chain, and N. Hubert (SOLEIL) showed a detailed study of the effect of temperature and humidity on RF cables’ transmission. He showed that some cables are very sensitive to external condition and special care should be taken when choosing a type of RF cable. Finally, G. Kube (DESY) showed how he was able to characterize the precision of the BPM in PETRA using only measurement performed on the beam.

Topic 2: Beam loss monitors

Other topics related to beam diagnostics were mentioned. A. Olmos presented beam loss measurements using a scintillating fiber at ALBA, while N. Hubert talked about their recent installation of new beam loss monitors.

Topic 3: Longitudinal beam diagnostics

Longitudinal beam profile measurements at SACLA were discussed by H. Maesaka from Spring-8. A. Novokshonov from European X-FEL presented the difficulties they had with coherent optical transition radiation and scintillating screens. M. Labat (SOLEIL) explained how they designed and installed a THz diagnostics beamline, and finally, L. Torino (ESRF) presented OASYS, a new software for synchrotron radiation simulations.

Topic 4: Discussion session

The workshop ended with a wrap summary, where it was discussed the real need for new hardware development. Modern technologies give access to more and more data, but a question on the

necessity of having all this data was raised. Finally, it was announced that the next DEELS will be hosted by ELETTRA Sinchrotrone Trieste in 2020 (which than later on cancelled due to the pandemic).

ARIES-ADA Topical Workshop
Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources
DEELS 2021
Online Workshop, July 7th to 8th, 2021
INDICO-site: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1027295/>
Workshop Summary

Editors: Hussain Al-Mohammad – SESAME, Ubaldo Iriso – ALBA-CELLS

10. Organised by:

Sponsored by:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under Grant Agreement No 730871

1. DEELS 2021: Workshop introduction and goals

During the last years, the Diagnostics Experts of European Light Sources meet together in a yearly workshop called DEELS to discuss common problems, share new developments, and enhance synergies between different facilities. The related style of a short workshop, but with regular yearly basis is well acknowledged by the participants. Since ARIES started to fund this meeting in 2019, the workshop has become an international forum including scientists from around the world (from America and Asia, and this time, also Africa).

Although in a virtual manner due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the workshop has been hosted for the first-time outside Europe by the colleagues from SESAME (Jordan) in the Middle-East. The meeting took place on 7th July 2021 with an extension to 8th of July, and up to 49 participants from 20 institutions were registered and 2 companies. We are glad to identify participants from private companies like "Instrumentation Technologies" and "Bergoz Instrumentation", and also from Universities in countries like Egypt or Pakistan. Due to the remote format the number of participants increased compared to the previous face-to-face meetings.

The workshop INDICO-site with all talks are available at <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1027295/> . The contribution comprises of a 20 minutes' talk followed by a 10 minutes' lively discussion. The workshop included a variety of topics inside the Diagnostics for Accelerators.

Topic 1: Beam Size Characterization and Machine Learning Applications

A first group of talks discussed the Accelerator Diagnostics using synchrotron radiation to monitor the beam transverse and longitudinal size.

11. Photon beam diagnostics at SESAME

Omar Al Kailani, SESAME, Allan, Jordan

In this first group of talks, Omar Al-Kailani (SESAME) reviewed the photon diagnostics currently in operation in SESAME, and the problems with them. The talk triggered a fruitful discussion with the different experts explaining the possible limitations of these diagnostics, including the appropriate materials for both vacuum windows and fluorescent screens.

Results with the Visible Light diagnostics with EBS now in full User-service mode

Elena Buratin, EBS-ESRF, Grenoble, France

Elena Buratin (EBS-ESRF) described the different diagnostics using the visible light to study the longitudinal beam distribution. The EBS, the first synchrotron in the world performing an upgrade from 3rd to 4th Generation of Light Sources, uses now a variety of instrumentation to monitor the bunch length during the injection and stored conditions.

Computer vision application for real-time beam tracking in pinhole image systems at ALBA

Andriy Nsych, ALBA-CELLS, Barcelona, Spain

A possible application of the Machine Learning (ML) for the beam size measurements in accelerators was introduced by Andriy Nosych (ALBA-CELLS). He developed a Artificial Neural Network (ANN) to identify the different beam images from an x-ray pinhole camera (see Fig. 1) and obtain the beam size from the analysis of the several images obtained from it. ML can be huge advantage in terms of precision, but with the bottleneck often found in this hot-topic: it is not easy to tune and train the model, and it often requires large time investments for its optimization.

Figure 1. The Artificial Neural Network (ANN) developed by A. Nosych (ALBA) is able to identify the 6 possible beam images, perform a 2-d Gaussian fit, and remove the corresponding Point Spread Function (PSF) to obtain a more precise beam size measurement.

Topic 2: Electronics for Accelerator Diagnostics

This second group of talks reviewed the status of different electronics developments specifically designed for Accelerator Diagnostics.

Experience with Pilot-tone+Libera Spark at ALBA

Laura Torino, ALBA-CELLS, Barcelona, Spain

Laura Torino (ALBA-CELLS) described the promising results obtained with the Pilot-Tone platform, which is designed to obtain a better beam position stability using the analysis of a reference signal. The solution is already commercially available from a collaboration between the private industry (iTech) and the Elettra Synchrotron.

Improvements of the bunch purity measurement at PETRA III

Kai-Oliver Demmler, DESY, Hamburg, Germany

On the other hand, Kai-Oliver Demmler (DESY) showed the home-made improvements carried out to a high frequency amplifier which, connected to an Avalanche PhotoDiode (APD), is able to measure the bunch purity in the order of $10E-5$. Nevertheless, this is still a work in progress as the project still tries to reduce the amplifier overshoot, and so still a better time resolution is possible.

Topic 3: X-ray Photon Beam Position Monitors

In this workshop, a significant discussion topic was triggered after the contributions of Chris Bloomerg (DIAMOND) and Marie Labat (SOLEIL) about X-ray BPMs.

XBPM temperature interlocks for DLS-II

Chris Bloomer, DLS, Didcot, UK

Chris Bloomer described the temperature interlock reliability in the XBPMs installed in the Diamond Light Source (DLS). Due to the flux/power distribution, the sensitivity of the XBPM temperature can be improved using a better mechanical design. This upgrade becomes a requirement for the future upgrade of Diamond due to the changes in the flux/power distribution.

About XBPMs for SOLEIL upgrade

Marie Labat, SOLEIL, Gif-sur-Yvette, France

Actually, in view of the upgrade of Soleil towards 4th Generation of Light Source, Marie Labat did a thorough review of the state-of-the-art in the XBPMs technology to conclude that the best strategy for the Soleil Upgrade will be the use of four-diamond blades in photo-conductive mode (for planar Insertion Devices), or else use diamond imaging (for Helical undulators). This raised the point among the audience to design a common strategy in the design of the future XBPMs, since many European 3rd generation light sources like ALBA, Diamond, Soleil or Petra-IV are currently designing upgrades towards 4th generation light sources.

Conclusion

The workshop also showed a general overview of the SESAME accelerator. The audience were not only impressed by the progress made for this light source in terms of resources/results, but also by the use of solar panels to supply the required energy for this machine. This is a clear example about the use of green energy in the accelerator environment. Finally, the workshop ended with a wrap-up summary of a very fruitful workshop, and with the common wish to meet in person once this Covid-19 pandemic is over. All the DEELS community hopes this will be soon.